

D4.2 | Evaluation of the first round of demonstrations

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Executive Summary

Within the SOTERIA project, alpha releases of created solutions to enhance road safety of vulnerable road users (VRUs) have been created. These shall be tested to identify malfunctions of the alpha releases or additional functionalities which have been stated as desirable from potential users of the solutions. Seven SOTERIA solutions have been tested in four different Living Labs (LLs) within the first round of demonstrations. The evaluated solutions:

- help to navigate and move in traffic more safely,
- help to identify and locate traffic demand and traffic safety, and
- map and classify traffic incidents.

For comprehensibility, this deliverable first summarises technical aspects of the solutions first presented in deliverables D2.1 | Safe mobility data space and simulation platform and D2.2 | Explainable accident and demand prediction analytics as well as the current situations of VRUs in the Living Labs as described in deliverables D1.2 | Requirements and SOTERIA architecture and D1.3 | Learning material and output of co-creation activities. For each solution, different evaluation approaches have been adopted that help to assess the described functionalities of the solutions in deliverable D4.1 | Demonstrations planning guidelines.

The feedback from users or technical partners in the first round of demonstration is reviewed and analysed. These evaluations results allow to identify potential improvements for each solution. These improvements, for instance, include:

- adaptions to data transfer methods,
- adaptions to influences on the measuring accuracy of sensors,
- visualisation adjustments for better comprehension, and
- measurement-specific bugs.

Furthermore, the results help to highlight and rank the needs for adjustment. On the other hand, they partially allow to create benchmarks to quantify the improvement of solutions between the first and second round of demonstrations. Thereby, the results and conclusions drawn are the basis for more stable, comprehensible and user-friendly solutions for the second round of demonstrations within the SOTERIA project.

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Abbreviations & Acronyms

BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
FAPS	Fraunhofer IVI Accident Prevention Program
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LL	Living Lab
MHM	Micromobility Hazard Mapper
ML	Machine Learning
OTA	Over-The-Air
PE	Protective Equipment
PEAM	Protective Equipment Assessment Module
PM	Particulate Matter
SSA	Safe Speed Advisory
SD	Secure Digital
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SMDS	Safe Mobility Data Space
UI/UX	User Interface / User Experience
VR	Virtual Reality

1 Introduction

Within SOTERIA, different solutions are developed that help to enhance road safety especially for VRUs. The solutions follow different approaches to improve road safety, for instance by helping to move and navigate more safely in traffic, by better identifying risks or risky areas within the street network or by mapping risky types of situations. Previously, **seven solutions** have been considered for which **first alpha releases** are available for a first demonstration and evaluation, namely:

- accident prevention schooling for generation Z
- safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms
- effectiveness evaluation of protective equipment
- safe speed limit advice for micromobility users
- a tool for monitoring and predicting road usage
- integration of big data sources for road safety predictions and
- a safe and clean routing app.

These solutions were assessed in the four LLs established in Germany, Greece, Spain and the United Kingdom. The assessment results of the first alpha releases are documented in this deliverable and shall build the basis for the upcoming work for the second round of demonstration of the SOTERIA solutions.

In this deliverable D4.2, each solution and its corresponding LL are briefly presented to highlight current needs and road safety issues of the LL and how the solution can help to enhance road safety for VRUs. These presentations are a short recap of the technical aspects described in deliverables D2.1 | Safe mobility data space and simulation platform and D2.2 | Explainable accident and demand prediction analytics and of the LL description in D1.2 | Requirements and SOTERIA architecture and D1.3 | Learning material and output of co-creation activities, and both shall support the comprehensibility of this deliverable.

Further, the approaches adopted to assess the current alpha release of each solution are presented to identify technical or content-related potentials for improvement. The evaluation methods are derived from the identified research questions and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) formulated in deliverable D4.1 | Demonstrations planning guidelines. With the help of the gained results, conclusions can then finally be drawn on the necessary adjustments to be made until the next round of demonstrations within the SOTERIA project to ensure more powerful, comprehensible and user-friendly solutions.

2 Demonstrations evaluated in the first round

During the first round of demonstration, the alpha releases of seven solutions developed within SOTERIA shall be demonstrated and evaluated in the four LLs. In this section, the solutions and their provided functions within the alpha releases shall be shortly presented to improve the description comprehensibility, for instance, of their intention, target groups or functionality. A full presentation of the solutions can be reviewed in deliverable D4.1 | Demonstrations planning guidelines.

2.1 Accident prevention schooling for Generation Z

To meet the expectation of today’s children towards a modern accident prevention programme, an additional module within the existing **Fraunhofer IVI Accident Prevention Program (FAPS)** shall be created that uses **Virtual Reality (VR)** and provides an immersive experience. FAPS relies on the network of the **Prevention Council of the Free State of Saxony** to connect with schools that reported a need among their students to be trained in the risks of pedestrians and cyclists while in traffic. The prevention programme targets children between the ages of 10 and 16 years since this age group does not follow mandatory traffic safety programmes (like bicycle schools and bicycle driving licences) and since they face major changes in their mobility at this life stage (change of school, travelling longer distances, travelling alone) which have a major impact on their exposure to road traffic and lead to high accident rates in this age group.

Within the existing prevention school, students learn by means of real accident data collected within their school environment that can be used to reproduce static accident situations on a tablet and switch into the view of the different road users involved. The newly implemented VR module allows children to experience typical accident situations of cyclists and pedestrians in which they can adopt the perspective of each accident participant either driving or walking at the moment of the first impact (see Figure 1). Thereby, they shall experience the perspective of motorised drivers to better understand their sight limitations and obstructions which they cannot anticipate since they have no experience as drivers and especially not as truck drivers. Within SOTERIA, the **pedagogic concept and learning material** were created to embed the new module offering the immersive experience within the existing accident prevention programme and to offer children the opportunity to learn effectively of accident risks.

Figure 1: Example screenshots of accident situations displayed in the VR module, where a cyclist appears from a tree-lined avenue, a pedestrian appears in-between parked cars, and a cyclist moves through the blind spot of a turning truck (from left to right)

2.2 Safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms

Within SOTERIA, three solutions were developed to more safely include micromobility in road traffic. They focus on collecting data from micromobility users to detect and categorise hazardous situations as well as map them. The components shall be presented in the following subsections.

2.2.1 SOTERIA sensor kit

Improving the safety of VRUs may need more detailed data on VRU travel patterns, urban infrastructure, and interactions between VRUs and motorised traffic. In recent years, innovative technologies have been explored to monitor and ensure cyclists' safety through data collection and analysis. Therefore, the purpose of the **SOTERIA sensor kit** is to integrate several **sensors and microcontrollers on micro-vehicles**, enabling the collection of **heterogeneous contextual, vehicle handling, kinematics and environmental data** to minimise micromobility hazards for VRUs. Specifically, the kit is designed to capture a comprehensive range of data and transmit this data to cloud-based platforms for real-time monitoring and analysis. Effectively, field experiments for testing the SOTERIA sensor kit aim to collect the micro-level data from VRUs required to monitor and ensure the safety of vulnerable micromobility users on the road, primarily focusing on cyclists on the road.

In other words, the SOTERIA sensor kit integrates various sensors to collect data related to micromobility user conditions, environmental factors, and vehicle conditions. In the system architecture, Portenta H7 microcontroller represents the central control and the main data processing unit. It is compatible with various sensor modules and has high processing capabilities. Additionally, Nicla Sense ME board is responsible for collecting and transmitting various environmental and motion-related data to the Portenta H7 via a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) connectivity feature. It collects data on cyclist behaviour and movements using an accelerometer and gyroscope which are capable of detecting changes in speed, orientation, and stability. This information can be used to identify potential safety issues such as sudden swerves or falls. Also, the sensor kit collects environmental data such as temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, and air quality. Effectively, Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) technology (i.e. SIM28 GPS module) has been integrated into the sensor kit to provide highly accurate location data. The GNSS module is connected to the Portenta H7 via a serial communication protocol. On the other hand, Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) technology (i.e. LD14P LiDAR) is considered and integrated with the sensor kit to continuously measure the distance and proximity of the micro-vehicle equipped with the LiDAR to nearby objects. Also, portable and high-capacity power bank has been used to power the entire system. In the field experiments, the collected data from the different sensors of the system is stored on a locally installed and connected Secure Digital (SD) card. A sampling rate of 20 Hz has been defined for the main sensors of the kit (namely, accelerometer, gyroscope, environmental sensors and LiDAR) and this sampling rate is often used for physical activity studies and fall detection. Figure 2 shows the architecture of the SOTERIA sensor kit. The SOTERIA sensor kit is explained and presented in more detail in deliverable D3.1 | VRUs and micro-mobility safety services V1.

Figure 2: The architecture of the SOTERIA sensor kit

2.2.2 Micromobility Hazard Mapper (MHM)

Due to the increasing popularity of micromobility options, there is a need to further enhance safety and infrastructure for VRUs. Therefore, the rising importance of road and VRU safety has led to the development and implementation of several technological solutions aimed at reducing accidents and fatalities. Additionally, understanding the factors contributing to accidents involving VRUs is essential for implementing effective safety measures. By recording environmental data, cyclist behaviour, and interactions with vehicles such systems can contribute to a deeper understanding of accident causes, thus providing data-driven foundations for improved safety regulations and infrastructure development.

The users of micro vehicles need to have a more comprehensive understanding of the surrounding hazards and dangerous situations to be able to avoid risky locations and potential accidents. SOTERIA will develop multiple data-driven services that will assist VRUs to minimise errors in their decision making, to avoid exposure to hazardous situations and to receive proactive notifications for potential hazards. Effectively, MHM is capable of **warning micro-vehicles’ drivers about potential hazards** that may destabilise the vehicle or lead to a potential crash. Therefore, the MHM is designed and developed to identify areas with specific **infrastructure deficiencies** (i.e. potholes) and high numbers of **vehicle conflicts** (i.e. high share of heavy traffic). Additionally, this service helps in creating a holistic view of urban mobility by mapping high-risk areas and identifying high-conflict zones using inputs from various sensors.

Threshold based heuristics can be used for determining the traffic and road conditions (road surface anomaly detection). However, Machine Learning (ML) techniques are more robust and versatile as compared to threshold-based methods. On the other hand, vibration-based approaches represent the most common techniques used for road surface anomaly detection and classification. Therefore, the MHM mainly uses micro-level data collected from VRUs using the sensor kit for detecting infrastructure and traffic-related hazards. This collection of data includes information about the micro-vehicle status such as timestamp, location, acceleration, angular velocity, and proximity to the surrounding objects. Additionally, the MHM analyses and processes the collected data and uses ML-based techniques to label the input data and then to train ML models which can detect different types and severities of hazards. Figure 3 shows the architecture of the MHM which is explained and presented in more detail in D3.1 | VRUs and micro-mobility safety services V1.

Figure 3: The architecture of the micromobility hazard mapper (MHM)

2.2.3 CYC sensor kit

Based on the findings of the World Café workshops held in Chania and Igoumenitsa, Greece and the respective of the first co-creation workshop held at ELTA headquarters in Athens, Greece (see Figure 4) with the participation of executives from the central administration and representatives of Chania and Igoumenitsa branches (see deliverable D1.3 | Learning material and output of co-creation activities), our focus group for the first round of demonstrations was decided to be motorised couriers. According to our findings, road works, weather conditions, dangerous spots and poor air quality are among their main concerns for their health and safety. Hence, ELTA bikes (both in Chania and Igoumenitsa) have been equipped with prototype micro-vehicle sensor kits to gather real-time data relevant to the aforementioned risks.

Figure 4: Co-creation workshop held at ELTA headquarters in Athens, Greece

The rise of geolocated devices, the dropping prices and increase in the reliability of low-cost sensors offer new opportunities for gathering spatiotemporal data, complementing traditional methods and providing better insights into transportation patterns. However, available mobile network data to analyse pedestrians' and cyclists' trips, especially in dense urban areas, is very limited. To cover this gap, our **micro-vehicle sensor kit's** payload includes **air pollution metering**

equipment (particulate matter (PM)_x, temperature, humidity), **Global Positioning System (GPS)**, **accelerometer and gyroscope** collecting driver behaviour-related data (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: The architecture of the CYC sensor kit with batteries

A full description of the demonstration can be reviewed in Section 3.6 of deliverable D4.1 | Demonstrations planning guidelines and in Section 2.2 of deliverable D3.1 | VRUs and micro-mobility safety services V1.

2.2.4 REBO camera kit

REBO is a **bicycle mounted camera** developed by ONSEE to specifically fill the major data blind spot of what and where cyclists experience near misses or hazards that regularly go unreported and thus addressed. In the United Kingdom, cyclist fatalities have steadily declined, but serious injuries and pedal traffic are increasing. Conventional sources such as STATS19, which collects police-reported road traffic collision data in the United Kingdom and is the primary data source for road safety analysis, frequently under-report non-fatal cycling injuries. This means there is an increasing lack of data that could be used to drive targeted improvements to infrastructure and initiatives to get more people cycling.

REBO tackles this problem by enabling the creation of a network of cyclists that capture **real-time footage of issues from a cyclist’s perspective**. Mounted on either the handlebar or under the seat, the compact, Wi-Fi-enabled battery powered camera records continuously and allows users to bookmark GPS-located and timestamped moments with a simple handlebar-mounted wireless button. The bookmarking saves videos from **30 seconds before and after an incident**, allowing analysis of how incidents develop and captures the response of the cyclist afterwards. When users plug the camera in to charge, these videos are automatically uploaded to the cloud without user interaction.

Once on the cloud, users can view their incident videos online, and shared mapping of incidents can be done together with other users. Wide-area data of incidents from users allow mapping of key hotspots, and cross-referencing with accident and travel demand data to allow local authorities or road safety professionals to see locations with emerging safety issues before there are fatalities. REBO empowers cyclists, informs policy-makers, and enables data-driven infrastructure investments that ultimately save lives. It aligns with Vision Zero’s proactive approach to accident prevention.

2.3 Protective Equipment Assessment Module (PEAM)

Various measures and PE can be used by micromobility to improve their safety. Effectively, many governments established legislations regarding mandatory use of PE (i.e. helmets) to reduce micromobility-related injuries and mortality. Therefore, PE aims to enhance VRU safety, promote sustainable micromobility and reduce traffic accidents which involve VRUs.

The Protective Equipment Assessment Module (PEAM) is a **data-driven service** that will **evaluate the effectiveness of various types of PE** (i.e. helmet, high visibility clothing, gloves and glasses) used by VRUs according to the **status of the road network, environmental conditions and characteristics of VRUs**. This solution will analyse the advantages and efficiency of PE for VRUs and how effective they are for VRUs’ safety enhancement. Principally, the effectiveness of both collision prevention equipment (e.g. reflective accessories) as well as injury prevention equipment (e.g. helmet) will be assessed and this will give both cyclists and VRUs insight on effectiveness of PE and encourage them to wear and use such PE constantly while travelling.

Effectively, the PEAM relies on several procedures and techniques to collect the required data and analyse it before calculating and assessing the performance and efficiency of the PE. The data regarding the protective equipment used by VRUs (e.g. high visibility jacket, helmet, lighting and gloves) can be collected from users through pre- and post-trip questionnaires and the SOTERIA mobile app. However, other data collection methods and techniques may be considered in the next round of demonstrations. Additionally, detected hazards by the MHM may be integrated with questionnaire data for better assessment of the PE effectiveness. Figure 6 shows the architecture of the PEAM which is explained and presented in more detail in D3.1 | VRUs and micromobility safety services V1.

Figure 6: The architecture of the Protective Equipment Assessment Module (PEAM)

2.4 Safe speed limit advice for micromobility users

In general, the severity of accidents involving VRUs increases with the speed of micro vehicles. The Speed Advisory Module (SAM) will **regulate the speed of micro vehicles** according to the **status of the road, existence of hazards and potential accidents**. Based on micromobility hazard

maps and considering the safety aspect of different road conditions, users are informed about the safest speed limit when they approach the locations of such hazards or risks. This speed advice can be provided to the VRUs through different means (i.e. mobile app or an on-bike device) and this speed advice enhances the safety of VRUs as the calculated and suggested safe speed limits aim to minimise the severity of crashes by proactively notifying drivers of micro vehicles to decelerate when approaching hazards.

Effectively, SAM enhances VRU safety, facilitates safe travelling, promotes sustainable micromobility and reduces traffic accidents involving VRUs. It uses micro-level data collected from VRUs, potential hazards’ locations, road infrastructure and weather conditions to proactively notify and advise the drivers of micro vehicles to slow down when approaching hazards.

The SAM mainly uses **real-time data related to hazards** (made available by the MHM), **historical data for accident hotspots, path or road type and weather conditions**. However, the functionalities of the SAM require this data to be converted into categorical types after it has been collected, processed and analysed. Essentially, the SAM uses ML-based techniques to label the input data and then to train a model that can determine (i.e. through classification) the safe speed limit depending on the input data. Figure 7 shows the architecture of the SAM which is explained and presented in more detail in D3.1 | VRUs and micro-mobility safety services V1.

Figure 7: The architecture of the Speed Advisory Module (SAM)

2.5 Tool for monitoring and predicting road usage

Recent studies highlight the importance of considering both motorised and non-motorised traffic volumes when analysing accident causes and frequencies. They also emphasise the role of socio-demographic characteristics in accident rates. Efficient transportation planning requires accurate travel demand data, including socio-economic profiles, trip origins and destinations, purposes, transport modes, and routes. Traditional data collection methods, like household surveys and roadside interviews, have limitations such as reliance on user availability, potential inaccuracies, high costs, and infrequent updates.

The rise of geolocated devices offers new opportunities for gathering spatiotemporal data, complementing traditional methods and providing better insights into transportation patterns. However, mobile network data availability is limited in analysing pedestrians' and cyclists' trips, especially in dense urban areas.

The SOTERIA platform aims to overcome these limitations by deploying the travel demand module, which is designed to reconstruct detailed mobility patterns for entire populations within a study area. It includes **models that integrate mobile network data, micromobility services' data, connected vehicles' data, and geolocated app data** to estimate travel demand for both motorised and VRUs. The goal is to provide **detailed traffic intensity information, segmented by user group** (e.g. elderly, cyclists) **for road sections** to support policy-making processes aimed at boosting VRUs mobility in cities and improving road safety. This information is visualised through the Data Visualisation Module. A detailed description of the solution is provided in SOTERIA deliverable D2.2 | Explainable accident and demand prediction analytics. In addition, a full description of the demonstration can be reviewed in Section 3.1 of deliverable D4.1 | Demonstrations planning guidelines.

2.6 Leveraging novel data sources to analyse road safety

By merging data from sources such as accident reports, connected vehicles, traffic information, and environmental factors, this measure seeks to identify accident trends and root causes, especially focusing on VRUs. It also strives to establish a platform that continuously monitors accident hotspots and driver behaviour, which could lead to more targeted interventions for specific communities.

Nowadays, in many cities and regions road safety analysis primarily depends on conventional data sources such as police reports, insurance claims, and direct observations. While these sources provided valuable information, they were limited by their reactive nature, capturing data only after accidents had occurred. Furthermore, data from these sources often lacked consistency and detail, varying in accuracy and completeness. Collecting and processing this information was also labour-intensive, leading to delays in identifying accident trends and implementing timely interventions. Additionally, these traditional methods often failed to capture critical indicators of potential risks, such as near-misses or unsafe driving behaviours that did not result in reported accidents.

Leveraging novel data sources to analyse road safety is based on three modules that are briefly described below:

- **Accident data processing and analysis module:** This module focuses on **extracting and processing data from the Safe Mobility Data Space (SMDS)** to evaluate VRU safety. It processes raw and harmonised data to generate various types of information, including accident records, infrastructure details, connected vehicle data, and other relevant factors. Its outputs include identification of accident hotspots, frequency of harsh events and travel demand information.
- **Labelled graph module:** This module stores a structured labelled graph in a database, where **intersections are depicted as nodes and road sections as arcs**. Labels are assigned to these elements, capturing **information such as pedestrian crossings, traffic signals, and public transport stops**. Additionally, it integrates **data from connected vehicle**

events and travel demand data. This structured graph provides extensive data and insights for understanding and predicting accidents involving VRUs.

- **Data visualisation module:** The purpose of this module is the visualisation of the data stored in the labelled graph module as well as other information that is considered relevant for the safety of VRUs and decision making on possible countermeasures. Concretely, the data visualisation module is a dashboard designed to provide a comprehensive **interface for visualising and monitoring accident hotspots at sections and intersections, frequency of harsh events of different types and travel demand data** for different road user types at section level. It aims to give decision makers a holistic view of more conflicting areas for the safety of VRUs, as well as the opportunity to monitor safety Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

A more detailed description of these modules can be found in deliverable D2.1 | Safe Mobility Data Space and simulation platform.

2.7 Safe and clean routing app

Common routing apps usually present shortest, fastest or cheapest routes to users but do not necessarily represent the safest options. Therefore, the SOTERIA routing app shall provide users with safe and/or clean route options between their origin and destination. For the first round of pilot demonstrations, the selected target groups are cyclists and pedestrians in general since, on the one hand, the current trends in cycling accident numbers shall be targeted and, on the other hand, peoples' willingness to go by foot shall be promoted to again strengthen walking as a mode of transport. On subsequent releases of the app, more target groups are planned to be included to enhance inclusivity and increase the feedback from different user perspectives.

Within the app, the user has the ability to set the desired mode of transport and personal settings such as the accepted detour. The current alpha release of the app will only allow to propose safe routes and not yet clean routes, since the focus was set on the more complex provision of section-based risk estimations in a first step. In the beta release, the simpler provision of pollution information will be implemented.

The safe and clean routing app uses risk predictions derived from accident and pollution prediction models and incorporates the safety-oriented proactivity and nudge engine. Both shall be shortly explained. A more detailed description of backend-solutions and mock-ups of the app are presented in deliverable D3.2 | User information services V1.

2.7.1 Safety-oriented proactivity and nudge engine

The safety-oriented nudge engine is a server-side component that directly communicates with the SOTERIA app and based on context information, provides outputs that promote safety. This component is implemented using all the core principles of a specific behavioural scientific approach called “nudging” theory, enabling changes in the road users' behaviours through subtle interventions called **“nudges” without restricting the user's freedom of choice**. For the purposes of SOTERIA, all nudges are tailored towards safer and more sustainable travelling. The nudges can be introduced to the user in various forms like **pre-trip, post-trip safety related messages** (e.g. as displayed in Figure 8) that prompt the user to adopt safer travelling behaviours or can be even more subtle like interventions in the User Interface (UI) / User Experience (UX) design, **promoting safer pre-selected choices** and general safety through specific placement of features on the

application. A more detailed version of the safety-oriented proactivity and nudge engine is presented in deliverables D3.1 | VRUs and micro-mobility safety services V1 and D3.2 | User information services V1.

The component uses a classification of users based on the **information given during their registration on the app, travelling behaviour information collected through their trips** and also **real-time context information**. Based on this classification and the real-time context information, the algorithm implemented into the nudge engine filters and selects the most appropriate nudge for a specific situation to each respective user. Messages span from a large message pool that is created using specific features (mode of transport, trip status, user's adherence to nudges etc.).

The final goal of this component is not only to promote safer and cleaner travelling behaviours, but also measure the impact that nudges make to users. Hence, extended functionality will be added to the component (on-trip nudges, on app nudge assessment) and refinements of existing functionality will be assessed based on user feedback.

Figure 8 Example of nudge message promoting safe road behaviour

2.7.2 Generalised accident and pollution prediction models

Accident prediction models are mathematical models which allow to calculate the expected accident numbers for instance on a road section by taking into account various systematic effects of influencing factors. The used prediction models in the SOTERIA app are based on generalised linear models which allow to estimate the **aggregated effect of multivariate influences on accident frequencies**. Which influencing factors are implemented within the models depends on their ability to explain differences in accident frequencies and are identified within the stepwise creation of the models. Different models were created for pedestrian and cycling accidents to allow for a differentiated analysis of the road network with respect to the different modes of transport.

Finally, a measure to describe the **accident risk for each road section** as a basis for the safe routing app can be derived via the **comparison between the expected accident number from the models and the real accident numbers**. This measure is then annotated to each walkable / driveable road section integrated in the labelled graph (see also Section 2.5) for the routing. A more detailed description of the created accident prediction models can be reviewed in deliverable D2.2 | Explainable accident and demand prediction analytics; the underlying labelled graph for the routing is described in more detail in deliverable D2.1 | Safe mobility data space and simulation platform.

3 Living Labs (LLs) for demonstration evaluation

LLs function as test sites in which solutions created in SOTERIA can be evaluated in real traffic conditions. Especially in the first round of demonstrations, this helps to identify possible remaining faulty functions or desirable new functionalities to ensure user satisfaction and operator friendliness of the solutions.

LLs are situated in the **four European countries: Germany, Greece, Spain and the United Kingdom** (see Figure 9) in which the solutions mentioned in Section 2 will be tested. These are complemented by **network cities**, like **Wolverhampton** and **Munich**, in which first prototypes are tested by involved partners to reduce risks during the test phase or allow to set up a control group for alternative applications. In the following sections, the four LLs and corresponding network cities will be shortly presented to allow for an understanding why certain SOTERIA solutions are introduced in these cities / regions first.

Figure 9: Geographical overview of Living Labs (LLs)

3.1 LL in Madrid, Spain

Demonstrated solution(s)

- **A tool for monitoring and predicting road usage**
- **Leveraging novel data sources to analyse road safety**

Madrid has experienced social, cultural, demographic, and economic changes over recent decades that have influenced mobility patterns. Factors related to demographic growth, production systems, population dispersion, new urban developments, and new policies aimed at transforming Madrid into a more sustainable city are contributing to increased motorisation and greater mobility needs among people.

In the last years, micromobility, now boosted by the eruption of shared mobility services and the facilities of e-vehicles (scooters, skateboards, bikes, etc.), has gained popularity as a sustainable alternative to private cars. However, these forms of mobility are not always seen as valuable by all road users. From the safety point of view, they have some detractors. Urban mobility planners have adopted various positions to regulate the services and ensure the safety of all road users, ranging from creating segregated lanes for these vehicles to the total banning of the operation of e-scooters in general or in certain areas. Policy makers have faced dissensus about the appropriate measures even within each group of road users. For instance, while some cyclists defend the existence of segregated bike lanes to increase their safety by keeping them away from cars, others claim that these lead to a higher number of fatalities due to reduction of visibility in junctions, among other arguments. Data scarcity about the number and severity of accidents and the external factors leading to these make it difficult to assess the efficiency of different measures and interventions.

In 2021, the Governing Board of the Madrid City Council has approved a new Road Safety Plan to be applied between 2021 and 2030. The city has a strategic objective to move towards safe mobility, with zero tolerance for accidents, and promote road safety habits that allow safe travel. To achieve the main objective of Vision Zero, several intermediate objectives have been defined. One of these is the enhancement of technological resources in road safety. This objective focuses on improving the efficiency, versatility, and effectiveness of police operations to address new safety challenges effectively.

Access to new mobility data sources (e.g. mobile network data, operation data from shared mobility services, data from connected vehicles, etc.) opens new opportunities for the rigorous analysis of urban safety of the different road users. New data sources enable the reconstruction of road user routes and flows and the identification of incidents (e.g. sudden braking). These insights help uncover factors associated with higher accident probabilities, ultimately aiming to

identify hotspots. New data analysis and artificial intelligence techniques can be applied to exploit these data sources.

SOTERIA plans to exploit these opportunities through several technological solutions, which will be demonstrated within the Madrid LL. The Madrid LL will utilise these new data sources to identify travel demand flows and accident hot spots as well as systematically analyse the impact of safety measures. Through insights from this spatial analysis, the LL will develop tools for analysing and predicting road safety incidents in urban environments.

The LL aims to support the city of Madrid in its goal to enhance technological resources. Specifically, the LL will enable the city of Madrid to:

- identify road safety risks in key areas of the inner city by integrating accident reports with connected vehicle data;
- incorporate travel demand insights from novel data sources (including shared mobility operation data, connected vehicle data, and mobile network data) into the road safety analysis;
- predict potential high-risk events by identifying and mapping near-collision incidents and classifying city areas based on risk levels for VRUs.

Specifically, during the first round of demonstrations, we will test two different measures:

- a tool for monitoring and predicting road usage; and
- leveraging novel data sources to analyse road safety.

These measures will contribute to the first two points mentioned above. The third point will be addressed during the second round of demonstrations.

3.2 LL in Saxony and Network City of Munich, Germany

Demonstrated solution(s)

- **Accident prevention schooling for Generation Z**
- **Safe and clean routing app**

More than 4 million people live in the Federal State of Saxony, which is located in the eastern part of Germany. The biggest two Saxon cities are Dresden and Leipzig, both with more than half a million inhabitants. Both cities are characterised by a relatively young population and influenced by a high number of roughly 40 000 students living in each city. Not least, because of its many cultural and historical sights, Saxony topped the ranking of holiday destinations in Germany with

annually 20 million tourists. As a result, a relatively high modal share of pedestrians (~26 %) and cyclists (~18 %) can be found here. This, however, also influences accidents figures in Saxony. Within the Free State of Saxony, killed or severely injured cyclists have increased by 22 % in the past ten years, although in general killed and severely injured persons decreased by 7 % in the same period. Pedestrians, in contrast, show a reduction of killed and severely injured persons by 40 %. When focusing on different age groups, young people between the ages of 10 and 18 years stand out with an increase of killed and severely injured persons in road traffic by 11 %.

The accident trends, however, can mainly be due to the reduction of exposure of VRUs to traffic. Walking as a travel mode has decreased significantly in the past years and has been amplified by the Covid-19 pandemic while cycling only experienced a low impact by the pandemic and continued its increase afterwards.

Within SOTERIA, the city of Munich functions as control group in which the old accident prevention programme FAPS is implemented without the new VR module (see 2.1). Munich is the capital of the Federal State of Bavaria with a population of 1.5 million inhabitants and is, thereby, the third biggest city in Germany. Apart from the bigger city size, the traffic and accident situations are similar to Saxony. Cycling as travel mode increased significantly in the last decade and currently has the same modal share of 18 %, whereas walking has a slightly lower share of 24 %. With regard to accidents, the number of injured cyclists have increased in the past decade by 19 %, whereas the number of injured pedestrians decreased by 18 %.

Therefore, both in Saxony and in Munich, cyclists and especially younger road users shall be focused on and trained to travel safe. To support this, two SOTERIA solutions:

- the accident prevention schooling for generation Z and
- the safe and clean routing app

shall be demonstrated in the LL of Saxony and the network city of Munich. The solutions shall, furthermore, ensure cycling but also other active and sustainable travelling modes to remain attractive and safe.

3.3 LL in Chania and Igoumenitsa, Greece

Demonstrated solution(s)

- **Safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms**
- **Safe and clean routing app**

Data spanning over the past decade (2012-2021) in Greece that cover the regions of Epirus (that includes Igoumenitsa city) and Crete (that includes Chania city) sheds light into road safety challenges. In Epirus, there were 1310 accidents with 1,966 road collision casualties, responsible for 289 road deaths. Pedestrian casualties accounted for approximately 12 % of the total incidents. Focusing on data covering the last ten years (2012-2021) for Crete, there were 1,996 accidents, 2817 road collision casualties with 527 road deaths. Among them, there were 369 pedestrian casualties (13 %).

Two-wheelers often face challenges such as managing interactions between them and urban motorised traffic in complex urban environments. At the same time, two-wheelers share health and safety concerns on phenomena like air pollution, extreme weather conditions (e.g. rain and heatwaves), road surface conditions, dangerous spots, traffic conditions, high driving speeds on crosswalks, and unpredictable circumstances (e.g. road works and accidents). When it comes to motorised couriers (i.e. ELTA courier drivers), the aforementioned problems are intensified by the fact that this focus group operates under strict time constraints.

Based on the findings of our co-creation workshop with this focus group (i.e. motorised couriers), deliveries planning is done usually by the manager of the local ELTA branch who also informs the driver. Daily deliveries are known beforehand, so their optimal route can be planned. However, in the course of their working day, it is normal that drivers receive off-schedule notifications for pickups. Consequently, their schedule (and, hence, their route) can constantly change, depending on the proximity of the pickups to the scheduled deliveries so as to reduce the respective time and distance. Each courier driver serves a standard area, which she/he knows well, generating implications for the frequency of the notifications on dangerous spots.

Figure 10: ELTA courier bike with the installed CYC sensor kit in black casing

ELTA couriers' bikes were decided to be equipped with prototype sensor kits (see Figure 10), bearing low-cost sensors for air quality and road safety. Low-cost sensors seem like the only option for effectively (in economic terms) gathering data, since expensive sensors could prove too costly for an economically viable test solution, let alone that they are too bulky for mounting safely on a motorbike. The kit's payload consists of sensors measuring PM 0.1, PM 2.5, PM 10, temperature, humidity, along with an accelerometer and gyroscope. So, in the context of the Greek LL, we gather and utilise environmental data to identify air pollution urban hotspots. Furthermore, data from the accelerometer and gyroscope are used for unveiling dangerous areas

inside the city (rapid acceleration and deceleration, as well as big inclinations of the vehicle indicate accidents or near-misses, happening at a high-risk hotspot).

The Greek LL aims to identify:

- healthier urban routes for couriers by integrating air-pollution reports into their route planning; and
- potential high-risk spots by mapping driver behaviours.

In a nutshell, both in Chania and in Igoumenitsa, couriers’ bikes are equipped with prototype sensor kits that bear low-cost air quality measuring and road safety payload, that can give us data for facilitating clean and safe routing for SOTERIA VRUs. Safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms shall also be addressed in the specific LL.

3.4 LL in Oxfordshire and Network City of Wolverhampton, United Kingdom

Demonstrated solution(s)

- **SOTERIA sensor kit**
- **Micromobility hazard mapper**
- **Safe speed limit advice for micromobility users**
- **REBO camera kit**

Oxfordshire in the United Kingdom is a unique proving ground for VRU related safety innovations due to both its advantageous regional characteristics as well as the fortunate position in having the county’s county council on board the SOTERIA project.

Situated in England, United Kingdom, it is notable for being the home of the University of Oxford, a place that attracts a high student and staff population that cycles, as well as the City of Oxford that has a network of narrow, historic streets, threading between tall medieval stone buildings through much of its center, a challenging environment for free-flowing motor vehicle traffic. At the same time, this serves as a welcoming environment for micro-vehicles and makes active travel particularly appealing.

The local government authority of OCC serves circa 700 000 residents (including around 165 000 in Oxford) and manages 4200 km of roads. Cycling is a strong part of the county’s transport culture: the City of Oxford has the second highest cycling rate in the United Kingdom with 35 % of residents cycling at least once a week, compared to the national average of 3 %. Despite its popularity, safety remains a major barrier to increasing cycling rates: 43 % of active cyclists in Oxfordshire identify traffic and junction safety as their primary concern. This highlights a key challenge for OCC who wants to increase the rate of active travel.

OCC’s commitment to Vision Zero – the elimination of deaths and serious injuries from road traffic collisions by 2050 – was agreed in 2022 with interim targets of a 25 % cut in casualties by 2026 and a 50 % reduction by 2030 before aiming to reach zero by 2050. Each year, Oxfordshire has around 30 000 accidents of all types, around 30 deaths, 245 serious injuries and 1250 slight injuries reported. Although the total number of casualties are declining year by year, the share of those by adult pedal cyclists are on a steady level. At some point, due to the declining casualty numbers in car drivers and passengers, achieving Vision Zero will have to switch the focus to VRUs, particularly cyclists whose casualties remain high.

Vision Zero’s philosophy is to eliminate road fatalities and serious injuries by designing safer systems, addressing existing risks, and proactively identifying and mitigating potential hazards. This is why this LL is focusing on proactive VRU safety data collection solutions, such as identifying near-misses, detecting leading indicators of VRU accidents, and preventative VRU behaviour changing solutions in the pilots. As part of technical development, UOW is a network city that provides a technical proving ground for solutions that could be deployed and benefited in Oxfordshire.

3.4.1 SOTERIA sensor kit

During the first round of the SOTERIA demonstrations, many field experiments were conducted in UOW, acting as a network city for the LL in Oxfordshire. The field experiments have been designed to test the performance and functionalities of the SOTERIA sensor kit solution developed by UOW. Effectively, these experiments and tests have been considered to support the evaluation of the SOTERIA measure related to the safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms.

Several test rides have been completed with one bicycle and one e-scooter which have been equipped with the SOTERIA sensor kit (see Figure 11). Effectively, some members of the project team in UOW have executed these test rides within the university campus and collected data by using the SOTERIA sensor kit. Therefore, the test rides and data collection process have been designed and completed to implement the SOTERIA sensor kit in a real testing environment and evaluate the performance of the system (i.e. data accuracy, frequency and integrity). Additionally, these ride tests aim to analyse the collected data and check the suitability of different sensor data collected to be used with micromobility safety services.

Figure 11: Photos of the sensor kit from the test rides at UOW

3.4.1.1 Micromobility hazard mapper

This SOTERIA component and related safety service require data from VRUs while operating micro-vehicles. Therefore, this requires installing many sensor kits on micro-vehicles (e.g. bicycles and e-scooters) to collect the data needed. The sensor kit may integrate accelerometer, gyroscope and proximity sensor and the collected data then can be used by MHM to detect infrastructure and traffic-based hazards. Given the limited number of SOTERIA sensor kits and micro-vehicles to be used for data collection, some publicly available open data (collected by sensors mounted on bicycles) has been used in the lab experiments to test the functionalities of this component and generate the ML-based models responsible for detecting different types and severities of hazards.

3.4.1.2 Effectiveness evaluation of PE

Assessing the effectiveness of PE requires data collection from VRUs including VRU characteristics and behaviours, used PE characteristics, encountered incidents and environmental conditions. Also, some input data is required from the MHM component such as type and severity of the hazards encountered by VRUs. The main role of the PE assessment module is related to the analysis process of the collected data to correlate the metrics related to the surroundings of a micro-vehicle with the characteristics and features of the used PE and then using this correlation for assessing the effectiveness of PE. Some of this required data needs to be received from other

SOTERIA services (i.e. the MHM) while other data needs to be collected through mobile-based questionnaires (i.e. SOTERIA mobile app) which should be deployed and distributed among micromobility users. Given the aforementioned limited number of sensor kits, synthesised data has been used in lab experiments carried out to test the functionalities of this component and to provide some guidance for the process of assessing PE's effectiveness.

3.4.1.3 Safe speed limit advice for micromobility users

The functionalities of SAM require data from MHM (i.e. real-time hazards) and from other SOTERIA components (i.e. historical accident hotspots and road types). Additionally, the SAM may need data from the SOTERIA sensor kit (i.e. weather conditions). Effectively, the main role of the speed advisory module is based on labelling the mentioned input data and using the labelled data for training ML-based models that can determine the safe speed limit at certain locations and conditions. However, the mentioned SOTERIA components and services are not fully functional or not really deployed to be used by micromobility users. Therefore, the alpha release of this component was tested using synthetic data. This allowed the implementation of lab experiments to test the functionalities of this component and the performance of the trained ML-based models used to estimate the safe speed limit.

3.4.1.4 REBO camera kit

The REBO system, loaned to cyclists situated in concentrated areas chosen within Oxfordshire, will enable the LL leading team to map high-risk cycling near miss hotspots, understand the context behind those hotspots and monitor emerging safety issues. By capturing 30 seconds of contextual footage before and after incidents, REBO allows detailed analysis of how incidents develop and the cyclists' immediate response. This data is automatically uploaded to the cloud by the users' own home internet. Once the cloud data is aggregated, it can be normalised via cyclist traffic volume data to get incident rate data, and cross referenced with additional accident data sources and tools to evaluate the effectiveness of near miss data in generating actionable insights above and beyond traditional reactive post-hoc accident data.

4 Demonstration evaluation in SOTERIA LLs

All SOTERIA solutions focus on enhancing road safety especially for VRUs. However, they differ in their approaches and target groups as well as their approach to evaluate the functionality of each solution during the first round of demonstration. This section, therefore, describes in a similar way for each solution:

- which information, e.g. on the functionality, impact, or accuracy of the solution shall be evaluated;
- which approach is used during the evaluation to achieve this information;
- what results could be obtained through the evaluation;
- which conclusion can be drawn from the evaluation to enhance the solution for the second round of evaluation.

4.1 Accident prevention schooling for Generation Z

4.1.1 Evaluation target, research questions

During the first round of demonstration of the new VR-module, the potential of the VR-glasses to enhance the existing FAPS programme shall be evaluated as well as different aspects of the usability of the VR-glasses assessed. Therefore, one focus lies on the differences in the general perception of FAPS with the old module (i.e. static situations reproduced on tablets) and the new module (i.e. dynamic situations reproduced on VR glasses). The other focus is set on the ability of the VR-glasses to be used by the children themselves so as to understand the situations they experience. In addition, it shall be evaluated if the VR-module helps to sensitise children to specific risks in road traffic more than the current prevention programme and if it can influence real-life behaviours of children.

4.1.2 Evaluation approach

In order to evaluate the effect of the new VR-module, both versions of the FAPS programme are carried out in Saxony as well as in the network city of Munich. In Munich, FAPS is implemented in schools with the static module whereas in schools in Saxony the new VR-module is used (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Testing of the VR module in a school

The implementation of both static and VR-module allows a direct comparison between the two versions. As a basis for the evaluation, a questionnaire is handed out to children directly after the prevention programme has taken place in the selected schools. Thereby, the questionnaire in Munich and Saxony consists of common questions which allow a direct comparison between the two versions. In addition, the questionnaire in Saxony is complemented by further questions which allow to assess the VR module in particular.

As common questions in both questionnaires, children are asked about:

- their perception of the type of learning and if they found it a diversified method of learning;
- if they would recommend this method of learning to others;
- which information or aspect of the prevention programme they particularly remembered;
- if they were able to draw conclusion for their own safety, safety behaviour or attitude towards road safety;
- their general perception of the prevention programme; and
- general strengths and weaknesses of the programme and suggestions for improvement.

In Saxony, the questionnaire included further complementing questions, focused on the VR module such as:

- if they were able to use the VR-glasses and the software by themselves;
- if the software was comprehensible;
- if the VR experience helped them to understand the particular risks of motorised road users towards the perception of pedestrians and cyclists; and
- if the time working with the VR glasses was sufficient.

To determine possible influencing factors, the location of the school (in rural/urban areas) and the type of secondary school (with children aged up to 10 years or 12 to 13 years with university entrance qualification) were collected. The complete questionnaire (translated to English) can be found in Appendix A.

4.1.3 Evaluation results

The initial phase of the LL demonstrations, which included the VR-module, was evaluated in two German locations: Munich and the surrounding area, as well as the Federal State of Saxony. In the following paragraphs, the German term 'gymnasium' will be used to define 'high school', and the participants of the 'Oberschule' will be referred to as 'secondary school' students.

In the city of Munich, 93 participants were surveyed, of whom 27 (29.03 %) were from high schools in an urban/municipal area and 66 (70.97 %) were from secondary schools in a rural location. The evaluation took place without the VR-module. In comparison, the VR-module was implemented in the Saxony region. A total of 154 participants were included in the study, of whom 110 (71.43 %) were from urban high schools and 44 (28.57 %) were from rural high schools. The following figures offer an in-depth examination of the specific elements of the evaluation process, with a detailed comparison of the findings from Munich and Saxony.

In general, the pupils approved of the FAPS irrespectively of the VR-module. Almost two third of the pupils in Munich found the program “good” or “rather good”. In Saxony, with the VR-module, even 93 % gave these statements towards the programme (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: A general overview of the opinion on the accident prevention programme (left: without VR-module (Munich), right: with VR-module (Saxony))

A total of 25.81 % of the respondents in Munich expressed a positive opinion regarding the learning approach employed by the accident prevention programme, with just 16.67% of those from urban high schools holding a similar view. 54.84 % of the participants expressed a positive opinion of the learning, with 33.33 % of this group coming from urban high schools and the remaining 66.67 % from rural secondary schools. In contrast, 17.20 % of respondents indicated a negative opinion of the learning, with 62.5 % of this group hailing from rural secondary schools. The positive feedback from the evaluation of the VR module in Saxony is even more pronounced than that observed in other regions, as illustrated on the right-hand side of the figure. Here, a mere 2.60 % of respondents indicated a lack of satisfaction with the learning methodology employed (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Outcome of the evaluation regarding if participants like the learning method (left: without VR-module (Munich), right: with VR-module (Saxony))

The consensus to transition from project-based work to the conventional curriculum is evident in both regions, though it is more pronounced in the context of the VR module's integration. About 72 % of all participants in Munich and over 81% of test subjects in Saxony found the project work a welcome change from usual lessons.

Figure 15: The project work is a welcome change from the typical format of lessons (left: without VR-module (Munich), right: with VR-module (Saxony))

The implementation of a VR module yielded significantly more favourable outcomes than those observed in the absence of such a module. In Munich, slightly more than half of respondents (53,76 %) indicated that they would recommend this accident prevention course to a friend. In Saxony, this figure was exceeded, with over 80 % of respondents indicating that they would recommend the course to a friend (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Recommendation following their participation in the accident prevention course (left: without VR-module (Munich), right: with VR-module (Saxony))

Figure 17 illustrates a comparable phenomenon. On the left-hand side, 16.13 % of respondents from Munich testing indicated that they believe this form of learning about accident prevention will have a long-lasting impact, while 6.67 % of urban respondents expressed this view. 41.94 % of respondents indicated that they intend to retain this information, while approximately 30 % of respondents indicated that they do not believe this form of learning about accident prevention will have a lasting effect. 11.83 % of respondents indicated that they will not remember this form of accident prevention learning. On the right-hand side, the acceptance rate for participants from Saxony is considerably higher due to the implementation of the VR module.

Figure 17: The learning process in the accident prevention course is characterised by a long-lasting nature (left: without VR-module (Munich), right: with VR-module (Saxony))

Furthermore, the results obtained with the VR module are more favourable, as illustrated in Figure 18 and Figure 19. The upper two pie charts demonstrate a greater focus on the matter of road safety (Figure 18), while the lower two charts illustrate the evolution of attitudes towards road safety among the participants (Figure 19). The data indicates that approximately half of all participants in Munich who do not have a VR module do not consider road safety in the future, whereas three quarters of those in Saxony who have tested the VR module do so.

Figure 18: The subject of road safety is a common topic of discussion in everyday life (left: without VR-module (Munich), right: with VR-module (Saxony))

Figure 19: The type of learning has influenced the attitude towards road safety (left: without VR-module (Munich), right: with VR-module (Saxony))

It is noteworthy that the participants from Saxony emphasised the considerable impact of the VR-module on changed attitudes towards road safety. The VR module was identified as the primary factor influencing attitude change by 80 % of respondents who indicated a shift in their perspective. Figure 20 illustrates the manner in which the VR module fosters a heightened sense of road safety among the participants.

Figure 20: The VR module was a significant contributing factor to this attitude (only with VR-module (Saxony))

Irrespectively of the good feedback for the VR-module, however, the open text field revealed possibilities for enhancement, such as:

- giving a little more time for the VR-module so that all students have enough time with the VR-glasses (currently two pupils need to share a pair of VR-glasses and the first user mostly gets more time) ;
- inserting a break after the introduction and before the VR-module; and
- adding further scenarios to the VR-module especially with further examples of the perspectives from car-drivers.

4.1.4 Conclusions

The accident prevention programme received favourable feedback, irrespective of whether the VR-module was utilised. The evaluation of the programme with a test group in Munich, however, revealed the higher potential of FAPS with the VR-module. The questionnaire revealed a stronger liking and impact, respectively, in most questions and therefore the high initial advantage of the SOTERIA solution. The project content has been well received and has generated considerable interest. This interest can be further expanded through smaller adaptations, which were given as individual responses in open text fields.

4.2 Safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms

4.2.1 SOTERIA sensor kit

4.2.1.1 Evaluation target and research questions

Testing of the SOTERIA sensor kit in the UOW represents one of the aspects related to the SOTERIA measure: Safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms. Therefore, the research questions this aspect aims to answer will focus on assessing the

performance of the developed SOTERIA sensor kit (one of the proposed solutions) without considering other solutions which might be involved in the same SOTERIA measure. Since the field experiments with the SOTERIA sensor kit have been completed by a limited number of staff members, the research questions focused more on the functionalities of the SOTERIA sensor kit, data quality and suitability rather than on the users' experience and their behavioural patterns. Thus, the research questions included the following:

- To what extent is the data collected by the SOTERIA sensor kit accurate?
- To what extent are the functionalities of the SOTERIA sensor kit stable?
- To what extent is the collected data by the SOTERIA sensor kit usable by the developed SOTERIA safety services?

4.2.1.2 Evaluation approach

The performance of the system's sensors is central to its functionality, yet sensor inaccuracies represent a persistent issue. These inaccuracies undermine the reliability of the data collected and reduce the system's ability to provide timely, accurate information in critical situations. Various techniques may be used to evaluate the functionalities and performance of the SOTERIA sensor kit in terms of stability, accuracy and useability. Effectively, data collected from the SOTERIA sensor kit can be processed, analysed and compared to a known reference position to measure the accuracy and stability of the system. Additionally, the data required from the sensor kit for the functionalities of other SOTERIA safety services (i.e. MHM and SAM) can be compared and linked to the data collected from the sensor kit to measure the useability of the SOTERIA sensor kit data. Thus, a hybrid approach involving a combination of techniques and procedures could be used to assess the performance of the SOTERIA sensor kit system.

4.2.1.3 Evaluation results

In the previous version of the system, ultrasonic sensors have been used as a proximity sensor, but it suffered from inaccuracies in outdoor environments. Also, the system's environmental sensor has been noted to fluctuate since the internal components of the system generate heat and the enclosure housing the system's components can lead to a build-up of heat. Therefore, the SOTERIA sensor kit has been upgraded and improved to overcome these limitations and inaccuracies. For example, the environmental sensors have been isolated from the internal heat sources, so the system's readings reflect actual external conditions rather than internal temperature fluctuations.

As a result of field testing and experiments on the upgraded version of the system, the environmental sensors provided stable and accurate readings (Figure 21). Additionally, the LiDAR is used as a proximity sensor, and it proved to provide stable and accurate readings, and no abnormalities or fluctuations have been observed in the collected data (see

Figure 22). Therefore, the system has the capability to warn the rider about the very close objects surrounding the vehicle (i.e. using a distance threshold). For example, the red circle in Figure 23 indicates that there is an object within less than one meter in the direction D45, while green circles refer to the existence of objects within a distance less than two meters from the micro vehicle. Additionally, this distance data may be collected and used by SOTERIA safety services (i.e. MHM) to detect obstacles and potential hazards on the road.

Figure 21: Sample of SOTERIA sensor kit data for environmental parameters (208 seconds data)

Figure 22: Sample of SOTERIA sensor kit data from the LiDAR (6 seconds data)

Figure 23: Sample of LiDAR data in the direction D45 (minimum value of 90 seconds data)

The field testing and experiments demonstrated that the data collected by the accelerometer and gyroscope were accurate and precisely reflected the movement of the vehicles and the behaviour of the riders. Figure 24 shows a sample of data collected by the accelerometer in axis z (i.e. vertical vibration) and the gyroscope in axis x (angular velocity). This data can be processed and analysed by SOTERIA safety services (i.e. MHM) to detect infrastructure and road anomalies such as potholes and curbs. For example, on the one hand, red circles in Figure 24 refer to a sharp change in the bicycle’s vertical vibration as well as in the angular velocity around lateral axis. On the other side,

Figure 25 shows a sample of data collected by the gyroscope in axis y and z (i.e. angular velocity around front and vertical axes respectively). This data along with other data (i.e. LiDAR data) can be processed and analysed by SOTERIA safety services (i.e. the MHM) to detect road anomalies (i.e. potholes), traffic conditions (i.e. obstacles) and rider’s behaviour (i.e. maneuver). For example, red circles in

Figure 25 refer to a sharp change in the bicycle’s angular velocity around front and vertical axes (i.e. rider’s swerving to avoid an obstacle).

Figure 24: Sample of SOTERIA sensor kit data from the accelerometer and gyroscope

Figure 25: Sample of SOTERIA sensor kit data from the gyroscope

4.2.1.4 Conclusions

The SOTERIA sensor kit developed by UOW has been tested throughout a number of field experiments to assess its performance. These experiments have been completed by a limited number of staff members to test the functionalities of the kit, data quality and the suitability of the collected data to be used by different SOTERIA safety services. Therefore, SOTERIA sensor kit data can be processed, analysed and compared to the requirements of different SOTERIA safety services (i.e. the micromobility hazards mapper) to evaluate the functionalities and performance of the SOTERIA sensor kit in terms of stability, accuracy and useability. The field experiments showed that the environmental sensors, LiDAR, accelerometer and gyroscope provided accurate readings, and no abnormalities have been observed in the collected data. Additionally, this data

complies largely with the data required by SOTERIA safety services (i.e. the MHM) to detect infrastructure and road anomalies (i.e. potholes), traffic conditions (i.e. obstacles) and rider's behaviour (i.e. maneuvers).

4.2.2 Micromobility hazard mapper (MHM)

4.2.2.1 Evaluation target and research questions

The sensor kit data (i.e. accelerometer, gyroscope and proximity sensor data) required for the functionalities of MHM are not yet available. As mentioned before, publicly available open data has been used in the lab experiments to test the functionalities of the MHM and generate ML-based models responsible for detecting different types and severities of hazards. Therefore, it is infeasible to answer the research questions related to the real demonstration and evaluate the relevant SOTERIA measure (inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms) before integrating and deploying the respective solutions. Accordingly, evaluation targets at this stage of the project may focus on the following:

- what types and severities of hazards can the micromobility hazard mapper detect?
- how accurate are the ML-based models generated to detect different types and severities of hazards?

4.2.2.2 Evaluation approach

The functionalities of MHM will be evaluated by running many lab experiments with publicly available open data. Effectively, the derived results from these experiments may be highly related to the input data used. Therefore, the input data determines the optimal number of data clusters (i.e. how many hazard types and severities can be defined) and the accuracy of classification algorithms. Effectively, the evaluation method includes the investigation of the procedures required for data preparation such as data cleaning, processing and analysis. Also, it covers ML-based techniques to label this data and then to train this labelled data and provide the ML-based models for hazard detection. Many ML algorithms will be used and their accuracy to detect hazards will be compared.

4.2.2.3 Evaluation results

The results of the lab experiments related to the MHM will be shown here to demonstrate the performance of its functionalities. The MHM mainly relies on the sensor kit data to detect hazards related to road infrastructure and traffic conditions (i.e. potholes, obstacles and heavy traffic) by using ML-based techniques. Effectively, the accelerometer (vertical axis) and gyroscope (lateral axis) data represents the vibration of the micro-vehicle and, therefore, they can be used to detect road potholes and roughness. Additionally, the gyroscope (front and vertical axes) and proximity sensor data represents the swerving of the micro-vehicle and, therefore, they can be used to detect road potholes, obstacles and heavy traffic. For example, Figure 26 shows how the sensor data can be labelled according to hazard type and severity by using ML-based techniques (i.e. clustering and elbow curve method). However, the input data determines the ranges of these hazards and severities (data clusters). It has been assumed that each hazard type has three severities (low, medium and high). The labelled data are then used to train ML-based models and specifically, classification models, which can be used in the hazard detection process. For example, Figure 27 shows that most of the ML algorithms tested to detect road hazards have great detection accuracy.

Figure 26: Example of sensor data labelling using ML-based clustering

Figure 27: Accuracy of ML classification algorithms

```
## Accelerometer_z & Gyroscope_x - Road Roughness and Potholes
# =====
#
#           Model  Training Accuracy %  Testing Accuracy %
# 0      Logistic Regression           67.80           66.14
# 1      K-nearest neighbors           99.11           98.29
# 2      Support Vector Machine        95.67           95.70
# 3      Decision Tree Classifier      100.00           99.24
# 4      Random Forest Classifier      100.00           99.68
# =====

## Gyroscope_y & Gyroscope_z - Potholes, Obstacles and Heavy traffic
# =====
#
#           Model  Training Accuracy %  Testing Accuracy %
# 0      Logistic Regression           82.53           83.39
# 1      K-nearest neighbors           86.16           82.25
# 2      Support Vector Machine        83.51           84.21
# 3      Decision Tree Classifier      100.00           76.88
# 4      Random Forest Classifier      100.00           80.61
# =====
```

4.2.2.4 Conclusions

The MHM has been tested by means of many lab experiments to assess its functionalities and performance. The lab experiments have used publicly available open data to find out the hazards that can be detected by the MHM. It has been concluded that accelerometer and gyroscope data can be used to detect road potholes and roughness while gyroscope and proximity sensor data can be used to detect potholes, obstacles and heavy traffic. Many ML algorithms for detecting hazards of different types and severity have been tested and almost all of ML classification algorithms provided great hazard detection accuracy.

4.2.3 CYC sensor kit

4.2.3.1 Evaluation target and research questions

Testing of the CYC sensor kit in Chania and Igoumenitsa represents one of the aspects related to the SOTERIA measure “Safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms”. At this stage of the experiment, research questions focus mainly on assessing the performance of the prototype CYC sensor kit.

The CYC sensor kit has been installed on three ELTA courier bikes and research questions focus on the functionality of the kit, the produced data quality and reliability, power management, the users’ experience and their behavioural patterns. Thus, research questions include the following:

- Are the functionalities of the CYC sensor kit stable enough?
- Is the collected data by the CYC sensor kit reliable?
- Is power management satisfying?
- What is the most effective transfer data method?
- How do motorised couriers prefer to be receiving their nudges? What do they consider more effective and safer?
- How often do we nudge them? After what number of repetitions of the same alert should we stop?
- Should we link the alerts type and frequency with risk intensity?

4.2.3.2 Evaluation approach

According to the manufacturer of air-quality sensors, the latter come calibrated. However, sensor inaccuracies represent a persistent issue, which needs to be addressed, since uncalibrated data may reduce the functionality and performance of the CYC sensor kit. That is why data collected from the CYC sensor kit must be processed, analysed and compared to a reference system (i.e. an air-quality station with calibrated, high-end, expensive sensors) to assess their accuracy. Additionally, the data required from the sensor kit for the functionalities of other SOTERIA safety services (i.e. the MHM and the SAM) can be compared and linked to the data collected from the sensor kit to measure the useability of the produced data. Thus, a hybrid approach involving a combination of techniques and procedures has been used to assess its performance.

As a first step, the CYC sensor kit was installed next to a reference station of the Technical University of Crete for three weeks. Analysing the data from the mounted PMx sensor of the kit and the data from PMx sensor of the reference station, a linear calibration function has been applied to the data produced by the CYC sensor kit. This step was critical for our data reliability.

Trying to extend the power autonomy of the kit as much as possible, its power module (battery set) has been designed so as to carry five sets of two identical rechargeable batteries. The environmental sensors have been positioned in a fair distance from internal heat sources. Effectively, the temperature and humidity data produced reflect true outdoors (rather than internal, inside the courier bike’s box) environmental conditions fluctuations.

The sensor kit PM sensor collects environmental data (PMx) every minute. The sensing interval remains under investigation, trying to optimise the balance between data reliability and effective power management. The CYC sensor kit includes a GPS module, which captures the precise location of data measurements. It includes latitude and longitude coordinates in decimal degrees format. The CYC sensor kit includes a time module too, which captures the precise timestamp of

the measurement point. The timestamp field records the exact date and time any incident occurs. It follows the format of YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS.

After the installation of the kits and the application of data reliability algorithms, the next challenge is the data transfer from the CYC sensor kit to a local (CYC) server. First of all, the kit checks the reliability of the preconfigured wireless network. The ELTA courier bikes equipped with the CYC sensor kit must be parked in an area with strong Wi-Fi signal, even more so during the reconnection of the charged batteries to the sensor kits. After that, the bikes must remain still for at least five minutes since the kits receive necessary initialisation information from the Wi-Fi network.

For measuring the acceleration of the bike in urban environments, a sampling rate of 10 to 60 Hz was anticipated. However, the sampling rate has a serious effect on the size of the received data from the accelerometer and gyroscope and the received data from these sensors may be too bulky. Consequently, the transfer of these data to the server is delayed or it is partial (not completely transferred). Besides, it has a significant impact on energy consumption which leads to increased frequency of battery charges. This may especially occur when the kit cannot locate a Wi-Fi network (because the bike is parked in an area without Wi-Fi coverage or because the drivers have changed their usual job timeline). In this case, the kit tries to connect to the preconfigured Wi-Fi without success, wasting energy resources and leading to an excessive energy consumption phenomenon.

As a workaround to the heavy data transfer problem, the sampling rate was reduced to 10 Hz. However, during the second round of demonstrations, other solutions, like real-time transfer of data from the kit to the server through a GSM network, should be tested and applied.

As far as the casing of the kit is concerned, after exhaustive testing, its design and material selection were finalised (see Figure 28). Furthermore, motorbike dimensions, weather conditions, optimal functionality and maintenance plan were taken into consideration in order to finalise the mounting method and positioning on the motorbike. Another constraint was that the casing needed to follow the arrangement and functional requirements of each sensor (e.g. optimal airflow for the PMx sensor but not too close to the bikes' exhaust). The batteries were separated from the main kits, positioned inside the courier bike trunk and connected to it with a proper cable. The kit itself is installed under the trunk. The casing also protects the sensors from weather conditions like rain and strong winds to further minimise the risk of damage.

Another aspect of our evaluation approach has to do with the findings of the workshop held in the LL of Chania and Igoumenitsa, in which potential users were questioned on their needs and preferences with regard to the SOTERIA solutions. This shall ensure that next to producing good quality data, the data is presented in a way that will be used by VRUs according to their needs.

Figure 28: Casing design of the CYC sensor kit

4.2.3.3 Evaluation results

Since the internal components of the system generate heat, the CYC sensor kit has been designed in a way to overcome possible data distortions. It has been already noticed that the environmental sensors measuring temperature and humidity need to be isolated from the internal heat sources, so the system's readings are not affected by them. This isolation was the result of field testing and multiple lab experiments. Effectively, the environmental sensors provide seemingly stable and accurate readings (see Figure 29 and Figure 30).

Figure 29: Temperature versus time during testing of the CYC sensor kit

Figure 30: Humidity versus time during testing of the CYC sensor kit

After the calibration of PMx data, data reliability proved to be optimal, considering that we are intendedly using low-cost sensors. Figure 31 shows a sample of data collected by the PMx sensor.

Figure 31: PM2.5 versus time during testing of the CYC sensor kit

Beyond environmental measurements, the data collected by the accelerometer and gyroscope reflected the bikes’ movements and the drivers’ behaviour. Figure 33 shows a sample of data collected by the accelerometer (along x, y and z axes) that can be utilised by other SOTERIA safety solutions (i.e. the MHM) so as to detect the drivers’ behaviour (i.e. sudden stops in specific spots). Apart from that, a sample of data collected by the gyroscope (see Figure 34) is presented in all three axes. This data, along with GPS data, can also be utilised by SOTERIA safety services (i.e. the MHM) to detect road anomalies (i.e. potholes), traffic conditions (i.e. obstacles) or drivers’ behaviour (i.e. maneuver), as shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32: Position of ELTA courier bikes where measurements were collected in Chania city between 12.09.2024 and 19.09.2024

In terms of users' behavioural patterns, the co-creation workshop which was held in the LL of Chania and Igoumenitsa and focused on motorised couriers subgroup provided valuable insights. The courier drivers seem to prefer to receive alerts and driving tips by voice or sound signal (the courier bike bears a Bluetooth device) or by vibration (e.g. from a wearable device). Also, bike drivers prefer to receive these alerts only in case of high-risk situations. Moreover, some alerts were suggested to pause after a certain number of repetitions (e.g. dangerous spots), because they may no longer be useful (i.e. the courier driver already knows this information from frequently crossing the hotspot and has been notified enough times). Also, suggestions were made for the frequency of alerts to be proportionate to the hazard severity.

Figure 33 Acceleration in x, y, z axes during testing of the CYC sensor kit

Figure 34: Gyroscope values in x, y, z axes during testing of the CYC sensor kit

4.2.3.4 Conclusions

The CYC sensor kit has been extensively tested in the lab before it was installed on three ELTA courier bikes in order to prove and improve its performance. After exhaustive field experiments, the environmental sensors, accelerometer and gyroscope seem to be providing accurate readings. CYC sensor kit data can be cleaned, processed, and analysed for the requirements of other SOTERIA safety services (i.e. the MHM). The data can be utilised in order to detect polluted areas

inside the city or to map infrastructure and road anomalies (potholes), heavy traffic conditions and bikers' behaviour (i.e. maneuvers or unexpected changes in speed).

ELTA courier drivers suggested that the nudge engine would also be useful in their work, provided that messages are received at reasonable frequency. They also stressed that hazards mapping should include as many hazards as possible and should include information about air quality, weather conditions, road works, special situations (e.g. roadblocks, accidents), and road surface conditions. The sharing of the hazard severity is another functionality that would be useful to them. Questionable driver's behaviour can be also addressed to a certain extent by tips, alerts and nudges. Conclusively, bearing in mind that they operate under tight time constraints, they shared that anything in the direction of improving their health and safety will be welcome.

4.2.4 REBO camera kit

4.2.4.1 Evaluation target and research questions

The demonstration of the REBO camera kit aims to explore how the system can be used to help improve VRU road safety (especially cyclists) by recording previously under- or unreported near miss incidents or hazards. We want to understand whether the data generated, when combined with other SOTERIA data sources, can be used to understand where near misses and hazards occur, how cyclists and other traffic participants interact during these events, what traffic elements and environmental factors these events take place in. If successful, we want to understand if these insights are sufficient to understand the root cause of these traffic conflicts. And on a larger scale, it is of interest if an aggregation of these factors is possible.

4.2.4.2 Evaluation approach

The first round of demonstrations was split into two phases: recruitment and deployment.

In the recruitment phase, we wanted to first confirm that people are interested in helping capture near-miss data in the first place. We designed a questionnaire to capture information about (see Figure 35):

- **cycling habits:** frequency, duration, routes, purpose of cycling, types of bicycles used
- **safety issues:** type and description of previously encountered incidents
- **interest in participating in the demonstration:** whether they are or not interested, if they require further onboarding, whether they're open to sharing data, and what their motivation for participating in the pilot is
- **demographic information:** gender, age group, abilities, ethnicity
- any other comments.

Figure 35: Questionnaire for the REBO camera kit

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL 'SOTERIA Oxfordshire Smart Camera'. The page has a navigation bar with 'Questions', 'Responses' (224), and 'Settings'. The main content area is titled 'Section 4 of 6' and contains a form for 'Pilot related questions'. The form includes a 'Description (optional)' field, a question: 'Have you encounter any safety issues or near misses on your rides before? As long as it affects you in any way, please describe these incidents.' with a 'Long-answer text' input field, and another question: 'Have you ever experienced any of the following while cycling? (Select all that apply)'. The second question has several checkboxes for options: Aggressive driving, Close passes by vehicles, Close passes by other non-powered vehicles, Poor road conditions, Incidents with pedestrians or other non-motorised wheeled users, Poorly marked cycling infrastructure, Poor or missing cycling infrastructure, and Other...

The aim of this questionnaire is to help us get a varied sample of users based on their cycling habits, demographics, and severity of current issues, and with the location information help cluster the demonstration so that we have a higher concentration of data points in key areas to aggregate numerous data collected during the demonstration. This combination allows to compare or integrate the data collected with existing data sets such as traffic flow data and accident hotspot data.

The questionnaire was sent out via OCC’s network both online and as paper fliers in public buildings. There was no major publicity for this recruitment campaign via social media or other media outlets as we wanted to “soft” launch this demonstration to test what the response of the public would look like before a later larger scale recruitment effort.

The second phase is to conduct a technical feasibility study of deploying the camera with users. This involved the assembly of a camera kit together with all relevant parts, including:

- REBO camera unit and wireless handlebar button;
- mount for the handlebar and back seat; and
- instruction manual to explain how to setup the camera on the bike, how to connect the software and how to get help if stuck (see Figure 36)

Figure 36: REBO camera kit

The kit was delivered in person, where the user was observed during the unboxing, installation and initial setup without input or intervention from us (see Figure 37). This allowed us to assess whether the user could install the camera kit without help, identify gaps in the instructions or kit, and the user’s enthusiasm for the kit.

Figure 37: User with installation instructions

Once installed, we focused on monitoring the system performance and user engagement. We monitored the data streams coming from the camera kit on the cloud platform to see if the user successfully uses the button to bookmark incidents, whether videos and GPS uploaded properly, and whether we could capture near misses and their context such as type of incidents, road participants, traffic elements etc. purely by playing the video.

By using this dual phase approach, we test not only the technical capabilities of the camera system but also how users interact with the camera and the trial. Overall, this aimed to ensure the system is technically functional and user friendly as well as that the trial is feasible. The first round of demonstration lays the groundwork for the later larger scale deployment with improvements in camera kit equipment and additional user-engagement details necessary for gathering a higher number of data points from cyclists.

4.2.4.3 Evaluation results

The questionnaire response was successful with 224 people responding even though the questionnaire was not heavily publicised. Given the large academic community in Oxford, the questionnaire study also included participants from the University of Oxford, who in the end, represented a large number of the sample.

The cycling habits of the recruits were very encouraging; almost half reported cycling every day, and there was a healthy split of reasons behind people’s use for their cycling journeys (see Figure 38 and Figure 39).

Figure 38: Stated cycling frequency

How often do you cycle?
224 responses

Figure 39: Stated motivation and trip purpose to cycle (multiple responses allowed)

In terms of location, we saw many recruits come from and to Oxford, but we did see a big cluster of people from Abingdon which is one of the major Oxfordshire towns. In terms of bikes, there were generally a big share of road bikes and hybrid bikes; there weren't many "specialty" bikes which may have made the mounting of the camera difficult (see Figure 40). This is all encouraging in terms of being able to capture lots of road miles within a few targeted areas, which is our initial objective.

Figure 40: Stated origin of trip

In terms of near-misses and interest in participating in the demonstration, there seems to be a strong tendency among responders to stress safety issues: the majority list close passes, poor

road conditions and aggressive driving as key issues, and many recruits wrote very detailed descriptions of their past safety issues when cycling (see Figure 41).

Figure 41: Stated cycling-related problems

This intrinsic motivation for this demonstration is also found when questioned if users are willing to test the REBO camera kit (see Figure 42), which will help us fulfill our objective of users' submitting their own incidents. The majority of recruits, when completing the survey, indicated they're ready to do the pilot, however a small majority wanted to receive additional information first.

Figure 42: Stated interest in participating in pilot

Are you interested in participating in the pilot?

224 responses

There was a strong interest expressed to learn more about the rest of the SOTERIA project too, with 72.1 % recruits having already signed up to the newsletter. There was sufficient demographic information submitted to diversify the participants’ selection, subject to any ethics consideration in due course.

In terms of the camera kit, the kit was handed over to a user in Oxford to identify possible installation issues. Unfortunately, the saddle had unconventional springs which interfered with the mount. However, the user was so motivated to make it work that they went to the bike store to buy a new compatible bike seat and continued assembling the camera kit. Once the new seat was installed, the user attempted to install the camera upside down which prompted our intervention. Eventually the user was able to complete the installation and rode away with the kit powered on (see Figure 43).

Figure 43: Installation steps and issues (from top left to bottom right): saddle obstructing camera mount, REBO camera upside down, correctly mounted REBO camera, user riding away

A few days later the user was able to successfully upload a video to the cloud platform, and our stats indicated the user successfully viewed those videos themselves on the platform. One of these videos highlight the successful capture of a close-pass incident (see Figure 44).

Figure 44: Recorded close-pass incident

It is useful to observe from the video (as shown in Figure 44) and further data (e.g. from the location – see Figure 45) the following information:

- the cargo the cyclist was carrying;
- their road positioning, being quite close to the edge of the road;
- that they're on the road;
- the time and location of the incident;
- the relative velocities and proximity of the vehicle;
- the make, company and registration of the vehicle;
- the road markings, i.e. no central marking on the road;
- the close pass incident despite the presence of a speed bump; and
- the 5 mph speed limit, which was being breached by the close passing vehicle.

Figure 45: Location of close-pass encounter

4.2.4.4 Conclusions

It was discovered from the first round of demonstrations that there are communication problems that need to be resolved with the user when installing the camera. Additionally, the seat mounting compatibility issue highlights the need to further explore mounting location variations that could cause issues on a larger scale deployment. Moreover, the footage captured looks good and demonstrates that the questions on how cyclists as well as other traffic participants interact during events and under what traffic and environmental conditions these events take place in can indeed be answered, and also that the initial observed characteristics from the videos can be segmented into initial metadata categories which can be further expanded as we discover more relevant factors which can be extracted from the videos.

4.3 Effectiveness evaluation of PE

4.3.1 Evaluation target and research questions

The PEAM requires data from different SOTERIA components including data about VRUs' characteristics and behaviours, PE used by the VRUs and the hazards which users may encounter in their trip. During this evaluation round, the focus was placed on the type of data that can be used for implementing a service that can be used for the evaluation of protective equipment. It was determined that data regarding statistics of how using PE affects accident avoidance and severe injuries and users' feedback on the PE used are needed. Accordingly, evaluation target at this stage of the project may focus on the following:

- What is the potential data that can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of PE and how can this data be collected?
- How can the effectiveness of protective equipment be measured / assessed (i.e. criteria)?

4.3.2 Evaluation approach

To answer the questions above, the functionalities of the PEAM have been evaluated by conducting a series of lab experiments with synthetic data. This artificially generated data resembles the final format of data expected before the assessment process and the results extraction. Effectively, the evaluation approach covers the investigation of the procedures required for data preparation such as data cleaning, categorisation, processing and analysis. Also, it includes the process of assessing the effectiveness of PE from processing to analysing data.

4.3.3 Evaluation results

The results of the lab experiments conducted for the assessment of the PEAM will be shown here to demonstrate the functionalities of the PEAM. The randomly generated data (Figure 46) used in these experiments and tests represent the data which is supposed to be collected from the VRUs by means of pre-trip and post-trip questionnaires after they have been cleaned, categorised, processed and analysed. In this data, the PE includes equipment that protects VRUs from potential injuries (e.g. helmet) and equipment that prevents accidents involving VRUs (e.g. high visibility clothing). Figure 47 shows the full list of the different PE considered and their categorisation. Effectively, data regarding the characteristics and behaviours of VRUs, the PE used, and accidents and hazards encountered can be collected from the VRUs and MHM and then used in the effectiveness assessment of these PE. Additionally, metrics related to the surroundings of a micro-vehicle will be correlated with the characteristics and features of used PE for assessing the effectiveness of the PE. Figure 48 shows the results of analysing data collected for assessing the effectiveness of PE.

Figure 46: Sample data for PE assessment

used_PE	VRU_behaviour	incident_cause	incident_severity	supportive_PE	VRU_mode	obstacle_severity	trip_duration
[1 elements]	neutral	not related	low	[1 elements]	positive	no incident	moderate
[1 elements]	positive	no incident	no incident	[1 elements]	neutral	no incident	moderate
[1 elements]	negative	not related	low	[1 elements]	positive	low	low
[1 elements]	positive	visibility	low	[1 elements]	positive	moderate	low
[3 elements]	positive	not related	moderate	[3 elements]	positive	low	low
[0 elements]	neutral	warning	low	[0 elements]	positive	high	moderate

Figure 47: PE considered for assessment

PE	Category
Helmet	Protective
Gloves	
Shatter-resistant protective glasses	
Body armour	
Elbow and knee pads	
High visibility clothing	Preventive
White headlight and rear reflector	
Reflective accessories	
Mirror	
Bell or horn	

Figure 48: Result of PE assessment

89.77% of VRUs who are wearing HIGH VISIBILITY CLOTHING did not experience any incidents (i.e. near misses)	64.78% of VRUs who are NOT wearing HIGH VISIBILITY CLOTHING did not experience any incidents (i.e. near misses)
--	--

4.3.4 Conclusions

The PEAM has been tested by means of many lab experiments to assess its functionalities and performance. In the lab experiments, randomly generated dummy data have used to identify key data types and potential data sources required for the effectiveness evaluation of PE. Data regarding the characteristics of VRUs and PE, the behaviour of VRUs, accidents and hazards enhances the process evaluating the PE effectiveness. Therefore, the generated data has been analysed and some metrics have been correlated to the characteristics of the considered PE to assess their effectiveness.

4.4 Safe speed limit advice for micromobility users

4.4.1 Evaluation target and research questions

The SAM requires data from different SOTERIA components including real-time hazards map, historical accident hotspots, road type and weather conditions. In a similar manner as in the case of PEAM presented above, during this evaluation round, the focus was placed on the type of data that can be used for implementing a fit-for-purpose service. It was determined that data regarding statistics of how VRUs manage speed advice and accidents and also data regarding the users' feedback on this service was needed. Accordingly, the evaluation target at this stage of the project was focused on the following questions:

- What is the optimal number of safe speed limits that can be used?
- How accurate is the ML-based model generated to determine the safe speed limit at a specific location and under defined conditions?

4.4.2 Evaluation approach

The functionalities of the speed advisory module will be evaluated by running lab experiments with synthetic data. Therefore, the derived results from these experiments (such as the optimal

number of safe speed limits and the accuracy of the ML-based classification models) may be highly related to the input data. Therefore, the input data determines the optimal number of safe speed limits that can be provided as advice or a notification to the micromobility users. Effectively, the evaluation covers the investigation of procedures required for data preparation, such as data cleaning, processing and analysis. Also, it includes ML-techniques to label this data and then, to train this labelled data and provide the ML-based models for estimating the safe speed limit. Many ML-based algorithms will be used to compare their accuracy to estimate safe speed limits.

4.4.3 Evaluation results

The results of the lab experiments related to the speed advisory are shown below to demonstrate the functionalities of the SAM. The SAM mainly relies on the synthetic data which needs to be first converted into categorical types (i.e. path type could be good, average or poor) before it can be used. Figure 49 shows a sample of this data required for the functionalities of the SAM. The data considered for the SAM include weather conditions, path type, road hazards, traffic hazards and historical accidents. ML-based techniques (i.e. clustering and elbow curve method) have been used to find the optimal number of safe speed limits that can be used and then to label the input data. The labelled data was used to train ML-based models (i.e. classification models) responsible for estimating the safe speed limit related to given input data. Although only randomly generated data was used and labelled, programming has been prepared to create ML-based algorithms to estimate safe speed limits, which can later be adapted to real-life data collected in the second round of demonstrations. Figure 50 shows the estimation accuracy of the different pre-programmed ML-based algorithms.

Figure 49: Sample of categorical input data randomly generated for the Safe Speed Advisory (SSA) module

vehicle_type	driver_cond...	PE_used	weather_condition	path_type	road_condition	traffic_condition	historical_accident
bicycle	positive	average	average	poor	NONE	NONE	NONE
bicycle	average	good	poor	poor	NONE	NONE	NONE
bicycle	negative	good	average	good	NONE	OB1	AH2
bicycle	average	poor	poor	poor	RF1	HT1	NONE
bicycle	positive	average	good	average	NONE	NONE	AH2
e-scooter	positive	poor	average	good	NONE	NONE	NONE

Figure 50: The accuracy of ML-based classification algorithms for the SSA module

```
## Weather_Codition, Path_Type, Road_Condition, Traffic_Condition &
## Historical_Accident - Safe Speed Limit Advices for Micromobility Users
# =====
#
#           Model  Training Accuracy %  Testing Accuracy %
# 0      Logistic Regression           53.85           55.55
# 1      K-nearest neighbors           99.25           98.28
# 2      Support Vector Machine        98.65           98.22
# 3      Decision Tree Classifier      100.00          100.00
# 4      Random Forest Classifier      100.00           99.98
# =====
```

4.4.4 Conclusions

The speed advisory module has been tested by means of many lab experiments to assess its functionalities and performance. In the lab experiments, randomly generated dummy data have been used to find out the optimal number of safe speed limits that can be estimated by the SSA module and to label the input data. However, the labelled data was used to train ML-based

classification models, which are able to estimate the safe speed limit. It has been concluded that the number of levels for the safe speed limits is highly related to the input data (i.e. elbow curve method). Additionally, many ML-based algorithms for estimating the safe speed limit have been tested and almost all of classification algorithms provided great estimation accuracy.

4.5 Tool for monitoring and predicting road usage

4.5.1 Evaluation target and research questions

The primary objective of this demonstration is to address the current information gap in mobility, with a particular emphasis on VRUs, by providing segmented traffic intensity data for each road section and intersection. This data is broken down by user group (e.g. elderly and cyclists) to enable a nuanced understanding of mobility patterns. The information is intended to support public authorities in road safety analysis and in shaping evidence-based policies that enhance road safety for all users.

The first round of demonstrations of this tool for monitoring and predicting road usage will focus on evaluating the utility and effectiveness of this data in helping public authorities with their responsibilities. Specifically, we aim to determine if the newly provided traffic data offers a substantial improvement over current data sources. Additionally, we will assess which mobility indicators, from a range of calculated options proven most valuable for public safety analysis and policy formulation. An essential aspect of this phase will also be to optimise the presentation of data within the visualisation tool to ensure it maximises user comprehension and decision-making impact. Furthermore, we will explore methods to derive relevant safety indicators directly from the mobility data, supporting a comprehensive approach to safety assessments.

The second phase of the demonstration will emphasise the accuracy and reliability of the data produced. This will involve validating the precision of the traffic and safety indicators to ensure their robustness for use in critical policy-making decisions.

The Research Questions (RQ) we aim to address through the demonstrations are as follows:

RQ1: How do various big data sources contribute to a comprehensive characterisation of urban mobility patterns?

It aims to evaluate the complementarities and synergies among mobile network data, connected vehicle data, shared mobility operation data, and travel surveys. This involves identifying the strengths and limitations of each data source in reconstructing mobility patterns. By integrating these datasets, we expect to provide a more detailed understanding of urban mobility patterns, offering key indicators such as the number of trips between zones, segmented by travel mode and user type.

RQ2: Can we identify the behavioural patterns of VRUs and how they interact with other mobility actors?

This question focuses on how we can support users in analysing the travel behaviours, preferences, and movement patterns of VRUs (e.g. pedestrians, cyclists, and elderly) and their interactions with motorised vehicles, public transportation, and other mobility actors. The goal is to enable a better understanding of the routes chosen by VRUs, helping to identify key interaction points, conflict zones with motorised traffic, and behavioural differences based on demographics and trip purposes. To facilitate this, we aim to provide traffic intensity indicators for road sections, segmented by user group and trip characteristics.

RQ3: Are there discernible temporal and spatial trends in VRU mobility behaviours and accident rates that can be identified through longitudinal analysis of big data sets?

This question focuses on how we can support users in analysing the evolution of VRU mobility patterns and accident occurrences over time and space, using longitudinal big data analysis. The expected impact is to inform the design and placement of VRU-friendly infrastructure (e.g. bike lanes, and pedestrian zones) based on long-term usage trends, as well as to assess the effectiveness of previous policies and interventions.

RQ4: How can we support policy making processes aimed at promoting micro-mobility within urban areas while concurrently enhancing safety for VRUs?

This question explores how indicators and data visualisation tools should be developed to maximise their utility for public authorities. We aim to provide a tool that effectively addresses their needs, enabling informed decision-making and improved policy development.

4.5.2 Evaluation approach

To test and evaluate this measure, we followed a qualitative approach. A workshop was held where the Madrid Municipal Police was invited to participate (see Figure 51), as they are one of the main potential users of this tool. The meeting took place on 25 October 2024 and was attended by the following participants from the Madrid Municipal Police:

- the person in charge of the Main Road Safety Department of the Madrid Municipal Police, who coordinates the writing of the Annual Accident Report for Madrid; and
- the Inspector of Road and Urban Analysis, who leads the department responsible for identifying and characterising accident hotspots in Madrid.

Figure 51: Workshop held at NOMMON premises with Madrid Municipal Police officers

The objectives of the meeting were to present the SOTERIA data visualisation tool, assess its potential impact and usefulness, and collect feedback to improve and add functionalities. Based on the feedback received, we plan to answer the above-listed research questions.

However, the quantitative evaluation of the results will take place during the second round of demonstrations.

4.5.3 Evaluation results

During the meeting, we presented the indicators generated by the travel demand module through the data visualisation tool. Examples of the indicators are shown in the following Figures 52, 53, and 54.

Figure 52: Visualisation of the travel demand information

Figure 53: Visualisation of the travel demand information of a street for the case of private cars

Figure 54: Visualisation of the travel demand information of a street for the case of micro-vehicles

The feedback that we received can be summarised as follows:

- Participants were very enthusiastic about the tool, believing it would be extremely useful. They noted that the administration should promote its use, as it can automate many tasks currently performed manually.
- The police officers emphasised the importance of georeferenced data and expressed a need for a tool that enables them to visualise hotspots quickly and easily.
- Currently, they do not consider travel demand as part of their safety analysis. However, they acknowledged that incorporating traffic flow data is crucial for road safety assessments. The travel demand information could be particularly valuable for identifying locations with accident rates higher than expected, based on their demand volume.

They also suggested the following improvements:

- adding more segmentation to the travel data, such as by age, trip purpose, or distance traveled;
- introducing a temporal filter for conducting longitudinal analyses;
- including a filter by district;
- enabling dynamic updates of statistics based on selected filters;
- improving the colour scale for better clarity;
- integrating demand information with accident / incident data to create a more robust indicator.

Overall, they were very pleased with the tool and recognised its potential to automate several tasks. They expressed a strong willingness to contribute to further development it and have already provided valuable insights towards this end. They plan to start using the tool immediately after the workshop, which will allow them to offer more comprehensive and detailed feedback.

4.5.4 Conclusions

The final user of the tool thinks the tool has great potential and can highly improve their current methodology. Regarding the research questions we formulated for the first demonstration, these were the following:

RQ1: How do various big data sources contribute to a comprehensive characterisation of urban mobility patterns?

Various big data sources each contribute unique insights into the characterisation of urban mobility patterns, each with its own strengths and limitations:

- Mobile network data provides a large sample size and offers daily information on mobility patterns. However, it has limitations such as the lack of certain user characteristics and it may lack sufficient spatial accuracy to accurately detect preferred travel routes.
- Surveys offer detailed information on user characteristics and travel behaviours but come with challenges like high costs, small sample sizes, and infrequent updates. Nevertheless, ML-based techniques have been shown to be effective in inferring some of this detailed user information to mobile network data, making it a valuable supplement.
- Connected vehicle data is a rapidly growing source that offers high spatial precision. It can be used to infer the routes of trips identified through mobile network data, providing a clearer picture of vehicle movements and interactions in urban environments.
- Shared mobility data functions similarly to connected vehicle data but focuses on the routes taken by micromobility services, such as shared bikes and e-scooters. This data is crucial for understanding the role of micromobility in urban transportation systems and its interaction with other forms of travel.

Together, these data sources provide complementary perspectives that, when integrated, enable a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of urban mobility patterns.

RQ2: Can we identify the behavioural patterns of VRUs and how they interact with other mobility actors?

We have successfully provided indicators of travel volume at the street level, which help in identifying the mobility patterns of VRUs and their interactions with other mobility actors. However, the precision of these indicators remains to be evaluated in the second round of demonstrations. This evaluation will help assess the accuracy and reliability of the data in capturing the behavioural patterns and interactions of VRUs with motorised vehicles, public transportation, and other mobility services.

RQ3: Are there discernible temporal and spatial trends in VRU mobility behaviours and accident rates that can be identified through longitudinal analysis of big data sets?

The current tool allows for spatial analysis of VRU mobility patterns and accident rates, providing valuable insights into spatial trends. However, we still need to improve how we present this information to make it easier for users to interpret the results and identify conflict zones. As for temporal analysis, we plan to address this in the second round of

demonstrations, where we will focus on evaluating time-based trends and their relationship to VRU mobility and accident occurrences.

RQ4: How can we support policymaking processes aimed at promoting micro-mobility within urban areas while concurrently enhancing safety for VRUs?

We have received feedback indicating that the tool has significant potential and could be very useful for stakeholders in supporting policymaking processes. However, there is still work to be done to improve various indicators, graphs, statistics, and the overall data visualisation. These improvements will help ensure that the tool provides clearer insights and more effective support for decision-making related to promoting micro-mobility and enhancing the safety of VRUs in urban areas.

4.6 Leveraging novel data sources to analyse road safety

4.6.1 Evaluation target and research questions

This SOTERIA measure aims to improve road safety by integrating diverse data sources for comprehensive traffic and accident insights, utilising advanced analytics to identify accident causes and develop targeted measures, and fostering collaboration among government, technical and research entities. At the measure level, it focuses on integrating data from various sources to estimate accident hotspots, driver behaviours, and vehicle movements.

This first round of demonstrations focused on evaluating both quantitatively and qualitatively the usefulness of three of the modules developed in WP2 | Advanced accident analysis and safety intelligence and described in Section 3.6. In Figures 55, 56 and 57, we provide screenshots of the different views of the tool evaluated for this measure.

Figure 55: Accident hotspot view of the SOTERIA accident data visualisation tool

Figure 56: Connected vehicle data view of the SOTERIA accident data visualisation tool

Figure 57: Travel demand data view of the SOTERIA accident data visualisation tool

To evaluate these modules, we posed the following research questions:

- To what extent are the rules used to establish accident hotspots accurate?
- To what extent does this measure reduce the cost and time required to estimate accident hotspots compared to the methods currently used by the competent authorities?

4.6.2 Evaluation approach

In order to test and evaluate this measure, as mentioned above, we followed a qualitative and quantitative approach. For the qualitative approach, a meeting was held with the Madrid Municipal Police, as they would be one of the main potential users of this tool. This meeting took place on 25 October 2024 and was attended by two officers from the Madrid Local Police. The objectives of the meeting were to present the SOTERIA accident data visualisation tool, assess its impact and usefulness, and collect feedback to improve and add functionalities.

For the quantitative analysis, we compare a subset of the accident hotspots identified by the methodology followed currently by the Municipal Police with the accident hotspots identified by the SOTERIA modules. To this end, we used the accident data of the Madrid urban area for years 2021, 2022 and 2023.

4.6.3 Evaluation results

In this section, we will first describe the qualitative evaluation that resulted from the meeting with the local police in Madrid. The main feedback that we received was the following:

- They were very enthusiastic about the tool, believing it would be extremely useful. They feel the administration should promote it, as they currently work manually, and this tool can automate many tasks.
- Several major hotspots identified by the tool match those already defined by the police, demonstrating the tool's usefulness and accuracy. However, in some locations, there was a small gap between the hotspots identified by the tool and the analogous ones identified by the police.
- They are very enthusiastic about the user type filter that allows the display of hotspots for specific users (e.g. pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists or general mobility).
- They believe connected vehicle data is very useful, and the distinction among the four types of events is appropriate. However, the visualisation should improve to make focusing on specific points easier.
- The travel demand information can be very valuable for identifying locations with a higher number of accidents than expected according to their demand volume.

Regarding the quantitative evaluation, we will show the results of the comparison between a subset of the hotspots identified by the police and the ones identified by the tool. The visual comparison can be seen in Figure 58 and Figure 59. Here, it is important to note that the location of the hotspots identified by the Madrid Municipal Police has been extracted using Google Maps geocoding service from the addresses provided by the police because the exact GPS coordinates were unavailable. As we can see in the evaluation results, all 20 accident hotspots identified by the police have a hotspot identified by the tool that matches perfectly or is very near, except for the two marked with a green rectangle in Figure 58. In this case, the Google Maps geocoding system did not assign the addresses to the specific intersections.

Figure 58: Hotspots identified by the SOTERIA modules (red) and by the Madrid Municipal Police (blue) near the Atocha train station

Figure 59: Hotspots identified by the SOTERIA modules (red) and by the Madrid Municipal Police (blue) in the Salamanca neighbourhood

4.6.4 Conclusions

In this subsection, we have described the testing of three components developed in SOTERIA: the accident data processing and analysis module, labelled graph module and data visualisation module. Specifically, we have used both qualitative and quantitative approaches for the assessment of these modules. The former consisted of a workshop with the Madrid Municipal Police in which we presented the tool developed and discussed with them the usefulness and potential improvements that can be made to the tool. The police officers were very enthusiastic about the tool. They found it very useful, and they also suggested improvements and further developments that we will consider for the next round of demonstrations, such as monthly updates of hotspots, functionalities to perform longitudinal analysis of interventions or additional filters, such as by district or accident cause. The quantitative analysis was based on the comparison of hotspots defined by the Madrid Municipal Police and the ones identified by the tool, using accident data from years 2021, 2022 and 2023. The results showed a high accuracy of the hotspots identified by the SOTERIA components.

4.7 Safe and clean routing app

4.7.1 Evaluation target and research questions

The safe and clean routing app comprises a set of different features which need to function altogether to propose an acceptable safe route option. Therefore, each feature as well as the interaction of these features will be assessed.

In the first round of demonstrations, the focus is mainly set on the correct functioning of the app with regard to possible bugs or shutdowns. The second focus lies on the assessment of each feature including the nudging engine, the underlying labelled graph, safety scores of links derived from the Generalised Linear Models (GLMs), and the routing engine within their intended range of functionality. The intended functionality of the app consists of:

- the setting of a road user type;
- the display of the current location on a map;
- the setting of a starting point and destination via the selection on the map or by address;
- the display of a fastest and safest route on the map;
- the provision of information on the two route options; and
- the provision of the current position and chosen route while using the app.

Figure 60 shows screenshots of the implemented features of providing fast and safe route options and the current position of the user along the route within the safe and clean routing app.

Figure 60: Provision of fast and safe routes (left) and current position along the route (right) within the safe and clean routing app

Next to the functionality, the evaluation shall also reveal desired or expected functionalities wherefore open questions on the handling and satisfaction of the app are posed to users and are evaluated for instance with respect to the installation and setting of the app or the perception of the app with regard to nudging frequencies or the time until a safe route is provided.

The previous involvement of users in an accident as well as information that help to characterise the user shall help to better understand or identify possible influences on the users replies.

The feedback during the first round of demonstration will help to enhance the alpha version of the safe routing app towards a stable version and highlight future features with a high to increase user friendliness and satisfaction. During the second round of demonstrations, a stable version with extended functionalities can then be used to research the apps ability to change the users behaviour towards choosing safer route options or help users to feel safer in traffic.

4.7.2 Evaluation approach

Analogously to the VR experience (see Section 4.1), the app was tested via a questionnaire (see English translation in Appendix B). Since a general functionality of the app was to be validated, only internal users at F-IVI tested the app. The questionnaire consists of a first block in which general information on the user's gender, travel behaviour, route decision-making and previous

involvement in an accident are retrieved. In order to classify the answers, this block is complemented with questions on the users' character such self-efficacy and locus of control.

The second block of the questionnaire focusses on the app experience. Instead of focusing on the individual features of the app, the questions are sorted by the "pre-trip" and "on-trip" phases and, furthermore, on the handling, safety perception and used street network. This shall allow more intuitive, non-technical and easy replies to the questionnaire.

Within the sub-block focused on "safety perception", the user shall rate if the provided safer route really felt safer than the provided faster route in order to draw conclusions on the safety estimates derived from the generalised linear models. The sub-block focused on "road network" allows to derive if the labelled graph consists of road sections or if the user is missing any links. Finally, the sub-blocks focused on "app handling", "pre-trip" and "on-trip" help to derive information on the correct functioning of the routing engine, the nudge engine and the app altogether combining several SOTERIA solutions. For instance, in the sub-block focused on the "pre-trip" phase, the user can state if the provided information helps to choose safer routes, is comprehensibly and is provided in sufficient time; within the sub-block focused on the "on-trip" phase, the user gives feedback on aspects of the nudge engine such as the comprehensibility and frequency of nudges received and, finally, in the sub-block dedicated to "app handling", general aspects on the app such as malfunctions and intuitive handling are questioned.

The whole questionnaire can be found in Appendix B.

4.7.3 Evaluation results

4.7.3.1 User profile

Prior to an examination of the questionnaire results, it is necessary to provide a summary of the demographic and statistical data pertaining to the test persons who attempted to utilise the initial iteration of the safe routing application.

- Most users were female, and the majority of journeys were of a relatively short distance with routes from 1 - 5 km (40 %) or 6 - 10 km (40 %). For distances exceeding 15 km, the preferred mode of transportation is the automobile. The shortest-range routes, with a distance of 1 - 5 km, were traversed by bicycle in three-quarters of all cases.
- The largest proportion of participants were identified as bicyclists (33.33 %), followed by pedestrians and car drivers (both 25 %) as well as passengers of public transport (16.67 %). No study participants were observed utilising e-scooters, motorcycles or miscellaneous micro-mobility vehicles as their most frequently used mode of transport.
- 60 % of all study participants indicated that they would value their proficiency level as a pedestrian as "extremely well", while 40 % rated their proficiency as "very well".
- With regard to proficiency as a bicyclist, 20 % rated their proficiency as "extremely well" or the best, 60 % rated their proficiency as "very well", 10 % rated their proficiency as "moderately well" and 10 % rated their proficiency as "slightly well".

It would be beneficial to ascertain the rationale behind the participants' selection of the conventional modes of transportation. Nevertheless, it is a detailed consideration of why the app subjects choose these vehicles or this mode of transportation. Shortly, the decision to travel by bicycle, automobile, public transport or on foot was influenced by considerations of road safety and surface conditions. It was observed that the weather, daytime and distance had no influence

on the choice of means of transport, even for pedestrians and cyclists. For pedestrians, the infrastructure was a more significant consideration, with participants citing that inclination and the height profile of the routes were key factors in their choice of travel mode. The visibility of these aspects in the app was deemed essential, as it would allow users to make informed decisions based on the most convenient route.

A significant number of respondents had previously encountered accidents while cycling, with a smaller proportion having experienced similar incidents while travelling by car or on foot. Those who had been involved in collisions with their bicycles have subsequently ceased to utilise it. This finding underscores the critical role that safety plays in determining the selection of optimal routes, particularly for pedestrians and cyclists.

4.7.3.2 Functionality of intended features

Concerning the intended functionality of the application, a suitable implementation was achieved.

The following potential improvements were highlighted by users:

- The application currently generates routes for both pedestrians and cyclists. It was noted that the app would benefit if the user could choose between pedestrian, cyclist or other modes of transport before requesting the route. As a positive side-effect, this choice would reduce the number of selectable routes and, in addition, this would reduce the number of routing queries to the routing engine.
- It was noted by users that the app frequently generates “zig-zag” routes which result in frequent turning-manoevres instead of staying on one street, crossing intersection in a straight line and reducing turning-manoevres to only one intersection. This has to be checked within the routing engine, if routes with a lower number of necessary turning manoeuvres can be prioritised in case of similar safety scores.
- Centering and display of the current location works very well, but in a few cases the zoom does not adapt and thus does not show the next manoeuvres (street names or turning points) and therefore, does not show the further route early enough.
- In a small number of cases, there were problems selecting a routing starting or ending at saved or stored addresses because the confirmation button was missing. This will be changed in the next version of the application.
- The display of the fastest and safest routes on the map worked but, from the users’ perspective, it would be preferable to allow for a better distinction between the two options. For this purpose, contrasting colour coding can be used.
- The provision of information on route options was largely seen as positive. However, the level of detail and usefulness can be improved to highlight the extent of the safety benefit more clearly, e.g. by displaying the increase of safety scores for the safest route.

In case of setting the road user type, one person remarked that it should be possible to choose between pedestrian, cyclist or other modes of transport before requesting the route. As a positive side effect, this would reduce the number of selectable routes and, in addition, this would reduce the number of routing queries to the routing engine.

In certain instances, the proposed routes disregarded restrictions for certain VRUs. This could be traced back to a false implementation of “null” values of the labelled graph into the routing engine and could be corrected.

Another comment involved the frequent proposition of “zig-zag” routes which result in frequent turning-maneuvers instead of staying on one street, crossing intersection in a straight line and reducing turning-maneuvers to only one intersection. This has to be checked within the routing engine and specifically, check if routes with a lower number of necessary turning-maneuvers can be prioritised in case of similar safety scores.

The centering and display of the current location works very well, but in a few cases the zoom does not adapt and thus does not show the next maneuvers (street names or turning points) and therefore does not show further parts of the route early enough.

When entering start and destination, the two points can only be selected on the map using 'Select from map' or there is no visual feedback for the selection. This point on the map cannot subsequently be changed or adjusted once the route is displayed under 'Find destination' without starting a new navigation. The only option is to enter it. Setting a start and destination point by entering an address works seamlessly. The next version will allow us to move back to the selection of destinations.

In a small number of cases, there were problems selecting a routing starting or ending at saved or stored addresses because the confirmation button was missing. This will be changed in the next version of the application.

The display of the fastest and safest routes on the map worked, but from the users' perspective it would be preferable to allow for a better distinction between both options. For this more contrasting colour coding can be used.

The provision of information on route options was largely seen as positive. However, the level of detail and usefulness can be improved to highlight the extent of the safety benefit more clearly e.g. by displaying the increase of safety scores for the safest route.

The performance of the application in terms of the provision of the user's current position and chosen route is satisfactory.

4.7.3.3 Potential for improvement and desired functionalities

This section presents a compilation of feedback received from individuals who participated in the inaugural demonstration of the safe routing application.

Although safety was a critical factor for users, a notable discrepancy emerged regarding the perceived safety of the proposed routes, with approximately half of the participants reporting that they did not perceive them as safer than their usual routes. When asked whether the route suggested by the app was actually safer than the shortest route or the expected route, 10 % responded with complete disagreement, 40 % and 20 % respectively disagreed or partially agreed, and only 30 % were convinced. None of the participants indicated that they fully agreed with the assertion that the route proposed by the application is more secure than the shortest or preferred route. To emphasise the safety benefits of the safer route in comparison to the fastest route and enhance the perception and selection of the safer route, it would be beneficial to display the safety score of both routes during route selection in the beta version of the app. This safety score could assist in determining whether to take the safer or faster route. The incorporation of a rationale that substantiates the assertion that the route is safer, for instance, by highlighting the avoidance of country roads, would be a further commendable enhancement.

A survey of users of the safe routing app revealed that the majority (66.67 %) considered the safest route to be "not too long", while 22.22 % regarded it as "fairly long" and 10% deemed it to be "too long". In the context of rush-hour traffic, it is imperative for most app users to avoid both excessive delays and taking a significant detour, which might compromise safety.

Approximately 45% of users indicated that the required time was not excessive. Conversely, a mere one-third of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the time required. While the required time appears to be acceptable, it has been posited that the application can present certain challenges to users. One already mentioned solution would be to narrow down the route proposition to one road user. Another solution could be the optimisation of processing speed, potentially through the reduction of data retrieval needs or the enhancement of the calculation of safest routes.

The incorporation of a feature that facilitates the storage and retrieval of pre-defined destinations was stated to enhance navigation efficiency by eliminating the need for re-entering addresses, thereby reducing the time required for navigation. The address search functionality should be enhanced through the incorporation of autocomplete suggestions and the acceleration of address entry to ensure a streamlined process.

The integration of voice-guided navigation as an available option was proposed, thereby enabling users to receive step-by-step spoken directions during navigation.

Furthermore, the incorporation of automatic zoom functionality at route intersections and during turns was recommended, with the aim of ensuring that users can more effectively visualise critical navigation points.

Given the numerous facts to be considered, the following section aims to provide a concise overview of the most significant recommendations received.

4.7.4 Conclusions

In summary, the intended functionalities of the application were achieved, and valuable feedback was obtained that hinted on possible further functionalities. The feedback from the participants gives several important insights and challenges related to the use of the navigation application to determine the safest routes. It is imperative to consider these observations and integrate them into the subsequent phase of the evaluation process. This will facilitate enhanced user involvement in the development of the safe route guidance application through direct feedback.

Since most users identified route safety as their primary concern, features for further improvement were indicated. A substantial proportion of participants identified deficiencies in the application's road network display, particularly driving restrictions, which have already been corrected.

Furthermore, they noted that the suggested safest routes were often winding, and it could be beneficial to reduce the number of turning maneuvers.

The fact that the safest and fastest routes were visually indistinguishable from one another has shown that more contrasting colours should be used. Furthermore, more detailed information on route options should be given to allow for an easier decision towards the safer route.

While the application is fulfilling its function in promoting safety, user feedback indicates that improvements in usability, route customisation and real-time support are necessary as well as solving technical issues during login and the entering of the destination.

The selection of improvements selected for the beta version of the application is based on the frequency of mentions, the feasibility of their implementation, and the expected impact on users' perception of the application.

5 Summary

Within the first round of demonstration, seven SOTERIA solutions, namely

- an accident prevention schooling for Generation Z;
- a safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms;
- an effectiveness evaluation of protective equipment;
- a safe speed limit advice for micromobility users;
- a tool for monitoring and predicting road usage;
- an integration of big data sources for road safety predictions; and
- a safe and clean routing app

were assessed in the four LLs situated in Germany, Greece, Spain and the United Kingdom. The solutions and corresponding LLs were briefly presented to highlight their need and their potential to improve road safety. Via a first demonstration of the solutions, bugs and errors, limited or desired additional functionalities were identified to create more powerful, comprehensible and user-friendly solutions.

The different solutions cover different aspects of road safety and provide different approaches to enhance road safety. Thus, the solutions require different evaluation approaches and follow different research questions which are further presented together with the drawn conclusions.

In the following sections, the conclusions and the identified needs for further development are summarised and provide the basis for the upcoming efforts for the second round of demonstrations of the SOTERIA solutions which will then be documented in deliverable D4.3 | Solutions impact assessment.

5.1 Accident prevention schooling for Generation Z

The FAPS generally received very good feedback. The survey approach that adopted for its evaluation allowed for a detailed comparison of how the programme was perceived, on the one hand, with a tablet-based module offering static perspective of road accidents (in Munich) and, on the other side, with a dynamic VR-based module (in Saxony). The comparison revealed the potential of FAPS with the VR-module, for example,

- when focusing on the general impression of the accident prevention programme;
- when considering the ability to change attitudes or safety behaviour; and
- when assessing the contribution to improve comprehensibility.

Although the project content has been well received and has gained the interest of students, adaptations will be made before the second round of demonstrations, especially regarding the available time for children to experience the VR-based module.

5.2 Safe and inclusive integration of micromobility to current mobility paradigms

The field experiments and evaluation of the SOTERIA sensor kit revealed that the environmental sensors, LiDAR, accelerometer and gyroscope provided accurate readings, and the collected data comply with the requirements of the MHM to detect infrastructure and road anomalies. Certain sensors of the system (e.g. LiDAR and GPS) require further improvement in terms of accuracy,

reliability and stability. Additionally, the system should provide the data collected in real-time to other SOTERIA services including the MHM. Therefore, sensor kit data needs to be transferred or uploaded to the cloud in real-time instead of storing this data on a local SD card. In the second round of demonstrations, the plan is to employ more participants who can use the system and collect more comprehensive data required for the functionalities of other SOTERIA components.

The MHM is designed and developed to use sensor kit data and identify areas with specific infrastructure deficiencies and high numbers of vehicle conflicts. Therefore, the MHM mainly uses accelerometer, gyroscope and proximity sensor data to detect infrastructure and traffic-based hazards. The lab experiments have used publicly available open data to find out the hazards that can be detected by the MHM. Numerous ML-based algorithms have been tested for detecting (type and severity) hazards and they provided great hazard detection accuracy. In the second round of demonstration, the functionalities of the MHM (including the ML-based techniques) will use complementary real-time data collected by the SOTERIA sensor kit instead of the open data used to train the related ML-based models. Effectively, the MHM may obtain real-time data from sensor kit and analyse this data to detect different types of hazards (i.e. road potholes, roughness, obstacles and heavy traffic) of different severities (i.e. low, medium and high).

The evaluation of the REBO sensor kit showed that data transfer is an important and timesaving feature. The sensor kit's Over the Air (OTA) updates functionality has been delivered and proved to be extremely timesaving for remote software upgrades, so it should be provided also in the second round of demonstrations.

The evaluation of the CYC sensor-kit indicated that data transfer should be possible in real-time and not be based on SD cards for temporary storage and Wi-Fi connection with the risks of low signal. The sensor kit should be equipped with Subscriber Identify Module (SIM) cards. The real-time data transfer will have an immediate positive impact on power management in sensor kit and, hence, on its usability (longer battery wear-out time, less frequent need for battery charging) and the solution's maintenance cost.

For the REBO camera demonstration, the recruitment work for test users has shown that the local population responded positively to our pilot demonstration efforts, and we should build on this warm welcome for the second demonstration phase. We should further publicise the demonstration and distribute the questionnaire to a wider group of people, particularly targeting students and staff at the University of Oxford and people residing within the Oxford and Abingdon areas.

For the physical camera kit, further refinement will have to be made to the onboarding instructions to make sure the kit is setup properly, and further investigation will have to be made to the edge case bicycle mounts to ensure compatibility with more types of bike handlebars and seats users may have. Continued refinement of the metadata categories will be made from analysis of any near-miss videos collected during the on-going demonstration. Once key compatibility and communication issues have been resolved, the next phase of demonstration will involve deploying the camera kit to gradually wider groups of people whilst monitoring any new problems we may face as we roll them out.

5.3 Effectiveness evaluation of protective equipment

The PEAM module has been tested by means of lab experiments and synthetic data to assess its functionalities and performance. Therefore, the key data types and potential data sources

required for the effectiveness evaluation of PE have been identified. This data may include the characteristics of VRUs and PE, the behaviour of VRUs and the accidents and hazards encountered by the VRUs. In the second round of demonstrations, the functionalities of the PEAM will use data collected from the micromobility users before they start their trip (i.e. pre-trip questionnaire) and after they complete their trip (post-trip questionnaire). Additionally, this data may include the outcomes of the MHM (i.e. obstacles). Therefore, this data may be analysed, and metrics may be correlated to the characteristics of the considered PE to assess their effectiveness.

5.4 Safe speed limit advice for micromobility users

Speed limit advice that aims to enhance road safety and the health of courier drivers shall include:

- dangerous weather phenomena;
- road surface slipperiness (for example, a drizzle might cause more dangerous road conditions than rain);
- dangerous spots;
- traffic conditions; and
- live update on emergency events (closed roads, accidents, if possible).

The SAM module has been tested by means of many lab experiments and synthetic data. The aim was to find out the optimal number of safe speed limits and then to estimate the safe speed limit appropriate to the input data. Many ML-based algorithms for estimating the safe speed limit have been tested and they proved to provide good accuracy. In the second round of demonstrations, the functionalities of SAM (including the ML-based technologies) will use data (i.e. hazards, environmental and infrastructure-related data) collected from different sources (e.g. MHM, sensor kit and OpenStreetMap data). However, other input data may be investigated and considered for the SAM including some aspects related to the VRUs, such as used PE (e.g. helmet and gloves) and used vehicle type (e.g. bicycle or e-scooter). Effectively, the SAM may obtain the required data in real-time and analyse the data to estimate safe speed limits (e.g. 12 mph).

5.5 Tool for monitoring and predicting road usage

The demonstration of the tool has confirmed its significant potential to enhance the methodology currently used by the final user. The tool effectively integrates various big data sources, such as mobile network data, surveys, connected vehicle data, and shared mobility data, providing a comprehensive understanding of urban mobility patterns. Each data source contributes unique insights to identify the mobility patterns of VRUs and their interactions with other mobility actors, offering valuable street-level indicators. However, further evaluation of the precision of these indicators will be conducted in the second round of demonstrations to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Additionally, the tool supports spatial analysis of VRU mobility, providing insights into trends and helping identify potential conflict zones. Temporal analysis, focusing on time-based trends, will be addressed in upcoming demonstrations.

Feedback from stakeholders has been positive with the tool recognised for its potential to support policy-making processes, particularly in promoting micro-mobility and enhancing VRU safety. Improvements in the accident data presentation are still needed to make the information more accessible to users and better support decision-making. This includes refining indicators, graphs, and overall data visualisation.

In conclusion, the tool is progressing well and shows promise for informing urban mobility planning and policy-making with further refinements required for maximum effectiveness.

5.6 Leveraging novel data sources to analyse road safety

The tool was demonstrated through a workshop with the representative of the Madrid Municipal Police, who were very enthusiastic about the system developed. Concretely, the system provides comprehensive VRU safety insights by leveraging novel data sources to estimate accident hotspots for different road user types, harsh braking event concentration at section and intersection levels, and travel demand for private vehicles and micromobility vehicles at section level.

The quantitative performance analysis showed that the comparison of hotspots defined by the Madrid Municipal Police and the ones identified by the tool, using accident data from 2021, 2022 and 2023, had a high degree of congruence. The tool itself was found very useful by the police officers who provided valuable suggestions for improvement and development, such as monthly updates of hotspots, the addition of functionalities to perform longitudinal analysis of interventions or additional filters, such as by district or accident cause, will be considered for the next round of demonstrations.

To summarise, the tool developed showed promising results, and the testing activities allowed us to gather valuable feedback that will be considered and incorporated in the beta release of the SOTERIA solutions for the second round of demonstrations.

5.7 Safe and clean routing app

The feedback drawn from the questionnaire revealed that the initially intended functionalities were achieved but various features of the application have the potential of further improvements.

The main improvements regarding key functionalities of the solution are the avoidance of zig-zag routes being generated and providing additional information regarding the rationale behind the generation of the safest route.

Initial suggestions regarding the user interface were related to a clearer distinction of route options in the map by their colour and improvements on the ways user can enter information (i.e. origin / destination points, settings etc.). Furthermore, default values for cycling and walking speeds need to be revised since an overestimation of necessary time for different routes was mentioned.

During the on-trip phase, real-time voice instructions are desired as well as the adaptation of the route if a user deviated from the initial route. By focusing on these improvements in future releases, the application can provide a smoother and user-friendly experience.

6 Conclusions

The results of the first round of demonstration of the SOTERIA solutions show promising approaches to improving road safety. The various tested solutions, which focus on aspects such as accident prevention, integration of micromobility, and real-time data analysis, have provided valuable insights that will be incorporated into the next development phase.

Feedback from the tests have indicated that the approaches not only raise awareness of safety risks but also contribute to the development of practical tools that meet user needs. In particular, adjustments based on user feedback, such as improving the user interface of the routing app and optimising the sensors in micromobility solutions, will be crucial in enhancing the effectiveness of the SOTERIA solutions.

The SOTERIA solutions have the potential to significantly increase road safety; however, further developments and adjustments are necessary to optimise usability and functionality. The next steps will focus on addressing these identified shortcomings and thoroughly pre-testing the solutions in preparation for the second round of demonstration.

Appendix A Questionnaire for VR-module experience

Figure 61: Questionnaire for the evaluation of the VR-module experience. Questions highlighted in grey colour were applicable only where the VR module was tested.

General perception	applies	Tends to apply	Tends not to apply	Does not apply	
Did you like the way you learnt?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Was the project work a change from the other lessons?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Would you recommend this accident prevention course to a friend?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Do you think that this way of learning about accident prevention will stay with you for a long time?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Have you derived any specific behaviors for safe driving from the project?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	If so, which?
Do you think that you will generally pay more attention to road-safe behavior for yourself and others in the future?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Has the project work changed your attitude towards road-safe behavior?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Did the VR application make a significant contribution to this?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Were you able to work independently with the VR glasses?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Was the VR application comprehensible overall?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Did the VR application help you to understand better?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Did you gain new insights into the perceptibility of pedestrians and cyclists?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Do you think that the VR application helped you significantly?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Would you have liked to spend more time on the VR application?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
What were you particularly interested in?					
What did you particularly remember?					
What did you particularly like about the way you learnt?					

Overall assessment	good	Rather good	Rather not good	Not good	strengths	weaknesses
General judgement on the accident prevention programme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •
What suggestions for improvement can you think of for the accident prevention programme?	Do you have any other comments?					
Are there any topics that you would have liked to see included in the project work but which were not covered?						
Do you have any other comments?						

Appendix B Questionnaire for the safe routing app

Figure 62: Questionnaire for the evaluation of the safe routing app

About you

To help us analyze and understand the data we receive from you it would be useful to know more about you.

Gender

- male female Non-binary / third gender Prefer not to say

Transport behavior

What is your most frequently used mode of transport

- car pedestrian cyclist public transport
 E-scooter motorcycle other

How far do you travel for most of your journeys?

- <1 km 1-5 km 6-10 km 10-15 km >15 km

How would you describe your proficiency as pedestrian?

- Not well at all Slightly well Moderately well Very well Extremely well

How would you describe your proficiency as cyclist?

- Not well at all Slightly well Moderately well Very well Extremely well

Is the choice of your travel route determined by the following?

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Safety of the route	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Travel distance	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Knowledge of the route	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Type of road infrastructure (e.g. roads, roundabouts, cycle facilities, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Road/Pavement surface conditions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Weather conditions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Time of day	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Character

This section is about your general outlook on life. There are no right or wrong answers in this section, just respond according to your feelings regarding each of the statements by ticking the answer that most closely matches your own outlook.

Self Efficacy	Not at all true	Hardly true	Moderately true	Exactly true
I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
When I am confronted with a problem, I can usually find several solutions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution to handle whatever comes my way.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Locus of control	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Whether or not I get to be a leader depends mostly on my ability.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
To a great extent my life is controlled by accidental happening.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I feel like what happens in my life is mostly determined by powerful people.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Whether or not I get into a car accident depends mostly on how good a driver I am.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
When I make plans, I am almost certain to make them work.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Often there is no chance of protecting my personal interest from bad luck happening.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
When I get what I want, it's usually because I'm lucky.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Although I might have good ability, I will not be given leadership responsibility without appealing to those in positions of power.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
How many friends I have depends on how nice a person I am.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I have often found that what is going to happen will happen.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My life is chiefly controlled by powerful others.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Whether or not I get into a car accident is mostly a matter of luck.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
People like me have very little chance of protecting our personal interests when they conflict with those of strong pressure groups.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
It is not always wise for me to plan too far ahead because many things turn out to be a matter of good or bad fortune.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Getting what I want requires pleasing those people above me.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Whether or not I get to be a leader depends on whether I am lucky enough to be in the right place at the right time.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Locus of control	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree
If important people were to decide they did not like me, I probably would not make any friends.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I can pretty much determine what will happen in my life.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am usually able to protect my personal interests.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Whether or not I get into a car accident depends mostly on the other driver.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
When I get what I want, it is usually because I worked hard for it.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
In order to have my plans work, I make sure that they fit in with the desires of people who have power over me.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My life is determined by my own actions.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
It is chiefly a matter of fate whether or not I have few friends or many friends.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Accident involvement

In the past 12 months, have you been personally involved in a road crash?

yes no

If yes, what was your mode of transport during the accident?

car pedestrian cyclist public transport
 E-scooter motorcycle other

The App

Safety perception

Do you think that provided alternative routes are really less risky than the shortest route or the route you had in mind?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

Road network

Are you missing some links in the road network for routing? If yes, please try to describe the missing routes

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

Pre-Trip

Do you find the suggested safer routes too long compared to the shortest route?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

Is the time between requesting a route and being provided with route options too long?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

Did the percentages of risk on each route affect your decision when making your choice?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

Do you find provided data for alternative safer routes helpful and more likely make you choose the safer route?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

If you disagree, which information would allow you to make your decision easier?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

App Handling

Do you find the handling of the app easy (Was the app easy to navigate and use during your trip?)

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

If you disagree, which navigation steps, do you find difficult?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

Did you experience any Bugs or Shutdowns? If yes, please describe at which steps during navigation settings or navigation the app did not work satisfactory.

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

Furthermore, how often did they occur, and did they significantly impact your experience?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

Did you find the amount of input you are able to change in the settings overwhelming?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

If you agree, which settings do you consider unnecessary?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

On-Trip

Did you find the nudges provided to you before and after the trip useful?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

Were the nudges too frequent?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

Is there any specific information you would like to be nudged about?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

Do you find the routing instructions during walking/cycling comprehensible?

- Strongly disagree Disagree Slightly disagree
 Slightly agree Agree Strongly agree

If you disagree, which instructions did you find misleading?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

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